

IMPACT HTA

Improved methods and actionable tools for enhancing HTA

Work Package 7 Deliverable 3 (D7.3): Testing the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework in collaboration with HTA agencies: Case studies on Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer and Spinal Muscular Atrophy

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Summary

Earlier research in Work Package 7 (WP7) led to the development of the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework, a quantitative decision analytic methodological approach, to help HTA agencies and evaluation committees using more structured and consistent processes in the evaluation of new medicines. Here we describe the adaptation of the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework with two HTA agency partners, the Swedish TLV and the Belgian INAMI, and its empirical testing with simulated HTA evaluation committees for two cases studies, one on Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC), and one on Spinal Muscular Atrophy (SMA).

Overall, four main methodological stages comprised a collaborative value modelling (CVM) approach, using a combination of preference elicitation means, including web-Delphi processes and decision conferences as part of a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methodology. Eventually, the framework was tested in practice with the case studies, which were in alignment with the ISPOR MCDA Good Practice Guidelines, following a two-step interactive value modelling process (an online web-questionnaire survey followed by a decision conference), engaging a group of experts from each HTA agency that simulated evaluation committees.

In the web-Delphi process engaging INAMI and TLV stakeholders, a preliminary generic list of 20 value aspects was supplemented with 3 additional aspects for INAMI, and 4 additional aspects for TLV, giving a total of 23 and 24 value aspects respectively, acting as the final HTA agency-specific lists of generic value aspects. In the first decision context (i.e. indication expansion in severe disease with a number of treatments available for INAMI, malignant neoplasm metastases for TLV), 12 value aspects were classified as “Essential”, 3 as “Influential”, and 8 as “Complementary” for INAMI; no value aspect was judged to be “Irrelevant”. For TLV, 5 value aspects were classified as “Essential”, 7 as “Influential”, 10 as “Complementary” and 2 as “Irrelevant” for TLV. In the second decision context (i.e. life threatening orphan disease with few symptomatic treatments and entry of new advanced therapy for INAMI, or motor neuron diseases and related disorders for TLV), 11 value aspects were classified as “Essential”, 6 as “Influential”, and 6 as “Complementary” for INAMI; again, no value aspect was judged to be “Irrelevant”. For TLV, 8 value aspects were classified as “Essential”, 7 as “Influential”, 7 as “Complementary” and 2 as “Irrelevant” for TLV.

The most substantial (proportional) change differences between the decision contexts within the same HTA agency took place for the value aspects classified as “Influential” with INAMI (n = 3 vs 6),

followed by the value aspects classified as “Essential” with TLV (n = 5 vs 8). In terms of the “Complementary” classification, TLV judged a larger number of such value aspects in both contexts (n = 10; n = 7) compared to INAMI (n = 8; n = 6). After combining the “Essential” and “Influential” value aspects together in a “high relevance” category and the “Complementary” and “Irrelevant” value aspects together in a “low relevance” category, a total of 15 “high relevance” value aspects and 8 “low relevance” value aspects were generated from INAMI in the first decision context, vs 12 and 12 from TLV respectively. Similarly, a total of 17 “high relevance” value aspects and 6 “low relevance” value aspects were generated from INAMI in the second decision context, vs 15 and 9 from TLV, indicating a larger number of “high relevance” value aspects with INAMI compared to TLV, and a larger number of “low relevance” value aspects with TLV compared to INAMI, in both decision contexts.

The two-step interactive process for the NSCLC case study initially involved a web-questionnaire to collect individual value judgments about the performance of three immunotherapies (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a chemotherapy (docetaxel), on five clinical value aspects. Nine INAMI and five TLV participants expressed separately their individual value judgements, with group majority judgements derived from them, based on which the prototype multicriteria value model was built. Following the first web-questionnaire step, an online decision conference took place (INAMI with 10 participants, TLV with 5 participants) to develop a shared multicriteria model and discuss its outputs, therefore enhancing the prototype model. Compared to the prototype model, treatments’ ranking based on the final results following the INAMI decision conference was changed, with Atezolizumab becoming second and Pembrolizumab dropping to third. Although differences also existed in the group’s value judgements following the TLV decision conference, any emerging changes in value scores and weights did not cause a change in the treatment’s ranking. Overall, differences existed in the final rankings between the two agencies, with Atezolizumab being ranked second followed by Pembrolizumab third in the case of INAMI, and vice versa for the case of TLV; with both agencies, Nivolumab ranked first, with docetaxel being last. In terms of relative weights, for the case of INAMI more than 1/3 of the model’s total weight corresponded to the Adverse events profile (36.3%), with about 1/4 of the model’s total weight corresponding to Duration of treatment effect(s) (22.7%), and then an equal weight for Impact of mortality, Impact on morbidity and Tolerability to patients (13.6%). For the case of TLV, just over 1/3 of the model’s weight corresponded to Impact on mortality (34.4%), with 1/4 corresponding to

Duration of treatment effect(s) (25%), just over 1/5 corresponding to Impact on morbidity (21.8%), 1/8 to Adverse events profile (12.5%) and less than 1/10 to Tolerability to patients (6.2%).

Similarly, the two-step interactive process for the SMA case study initially involved a web-questionnaire to collect individual value judgments about the performance of the treatments of interest (Zolgensma, Spinraza, and Evrysdi), relative to Best Supportive Care (BSC), on four or five clinical value aspects. Eight INAMI and six TLV participants expressed separately their individual value judgements, with group majority judgements being derived from them, based on which the prototype multicriteria value model 1 was built. Following the first web-questionnaire step, a virtual decision conference took place (INAMI with 8 participants, TLV with 5 participants) to develop a shared multicriteria model and discuss its outputs, therefore enhancing again the preliminary prototype model. Although differences existed in the group's value judgements following the INAMI decision conference, any emerging changes in value scores and weights did not result in a difference in the treatment's ranking. For the case of TLV, compared to the prototype model, treatments' ranking based on the final results following the decision conference was changed, with Evrysdi becoming second and Spinraza dropping to third. Overall, differences existed in the final (clinical) rankings between the two agencies, with Evrysdi being ranked first followed by Zolgensma in the case of INAMI, and vice versa for the case of TLV; with both agencies, Spinraza ranked third, followed by BSC. In terms of relative weights, for the case of INAMI more than 1/3 of the model's total weight corresponded to the Impact on mortality (35.7%), with an identical weight equal to 1/4 of the model's total corresponding to Tolerability to patients (25%) and Health Related Quality of Life (25%), and then Impact on morbidity (14.3%). For the case of TLV, just under 1/3 of the model's weight corresponded to Health Related Quality of Life (31.7%), and Impact on mortality (29.3%), with just over 1/5 corresponding to Impact on morbidity (22%), about 1/8 to Tolerability to patients (12.2%) and almost 1/20 to Tolerability to patients (4.9%). In terms of the SMA non-clinical value models, for the case of INAMI instead of Evrysdi which was the top-ranked option in terms of clinical value aspects, Zolgensma was the top-ranked option in terms of non-clinical value aspects, followed by Evrysdi and then by Spinraza. For the case of TLV, Zolgensma was also the top-ranked option in terms of non-clinical value aspects, having the same ranking with clinical value aspects.

The results indicate that what matters in the evaluation of new medicines for HTA agencies is not limited to their clinical benefits in terms of mortality and morbidity but represents a more

comprehensive concept, which could be captured by a number of clinical and non-clinical value aspects. This value concept becomes more complex given that value aspects and their degrees of relevance also vary between decision contexts, both in terms of evaluation within the same agencies or committees, but also between them. Therefore, HTA institutions would benefit from methodological tools that can be flexible enough to serve the individual needs of different HTA agencies but at the same time they should be characterized by some common value benchmarks in order to draw comparisons between evaluations.

The IMPACT-HTA value framework is characterized by a common but flexible value frame, which can be adapted according to individual HTA agency needs, being able to capture what matters to all relevant stakeholders and also by how much, given the ability to incorporate and elicit value trade-offs as part of an engaging socio-technical approach. Future research could focus on further empirical applications of the IMPACT-HTA value framework, in collaboration with HTA agencies and for different decision contexts, in order to better understand its potential benefits and limitations..

Background

Earlier research in Work Package 7 (WP7) using advanced econometric techniques generated an evidence-based model to better understand determinants of HTA coverage decisions, acting as predictors of HTA recommendations (WP7, Task 1).

Using these findings, in combination with further secondary data and primary evidence collection using a series of web-Delphi processes and workshops with relevant HTA stakeholders, led to the proposed IMPACT-HTA Value Framework to help HTA agencies and evaluation committees using more structured and consistent processes to evaluate medicines (WP7, Task 2).

This report outlines the testing of the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework, involving its adaptation for a number of specific disease contexts in collaboration with two HTA agencies (Swedish TLV and Belgian INAMI), followed by its application for two specific disease indications taking the form of empirical case studies (Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer, NSCLC, and Spinal Muscular Atrophy, SMA). The aim of the case studies was to test the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework in practice for supporting HTA agencies and health insurers in evaluating new treatments, by explicitly considering multiple value aspects and their trade-offs (WP7, Task 3). Furthermore, we provide a short discussion with some recommendations for resource allocation (WP7, Task 4). Overall, this deliverable (D7.3) corresponds to the report of Task 3 and Task 4.

In the next section we outline the Methods used (Task 3), in the following section we describe the generation and analysis of the Results (Task 3), and finally we provide a short discussion with some key policy implications (Task 4). Additional information with a detailed description of all stages is provided in the Supplementary material Appendix, taking the form of a slide deck.

Methods

Overview of the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework and its adaptation with HTA agencies (Stages 1-4): a Collaborative Value Modelling approach

The methods discussed in this section relate to Task 3 of WP7. The IMPACT-HTA Value Framework can be described by the following development, adaptation and testing cycle consisting of the following Phases: initially a set of relevant value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in the context of HTA were developed by utilizing literature findings, followed by a web-Delphi process with international stakeholders and a facilitated workshop with key representatives (Phase 1a). The resulting list of value aspects were then adapted from the perspective of two HTA agency partners, and by considering their relevance for the case of five specific disease and therapeutic areas through another web-Delphi process with HTA agency stakeholders (Phase 1b). The two HTA agency partners were the Swedish Dental and Pharmaceutical Benefits Agency (Tandvårds-och läkemedelsförmånsverket, TLV) and the Belgian National Health Insurance Agency (INAMI-RIZIV). The HTA-agency specific final list of value aspects and their relevance were then applied in practice to test the framework with simulated HTA evaluation committees by operationalizing the value aspects for two selected evaluation contexts (NSCLC and SMA), taking the form of empirical case studies via facilitated workshops (Phase 2). Finally, over continuing rounds of applications and testing, reflections and insights from participating HTA evaluation committee members should drive towards improving the value framework and evaluation procedures in place at HTA agency level (Phase 3). Below, the adaptation of the value aspects with INAMI and TLV is described (Phase 1b) by focusing on the results of two out of the five disease and therapeutic areas explored, followed by the empirical case studies (Phase 2).

Overall, four main methodological stages comprised a collaborative value modelling (CVM) approach(1), using a combination of preference elicitation means, including web-Delphi processes and decision conferences as part of a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) methodology(2). This CVM approach started with a consultation of the two HTA agency partners, followed by a web-Delphi process engaging HTA agencies' stakeholders, interviews at HTA agencies' senior level, and finally empirical case study applications with expert groups simulating HTA agency and payer

evaluation committees via facilitated workshops in the form of decision conferences (see Figure 1). These Stages are different to the above described Phases (all of which fall within Phases 1b and 2).

Figure 1: Overview of IMPACT-HTA Value Framework adaptation with HTA agencies using a Collaborative Value Modelling approach

In the first Stage, a validation of the preliminary list of the Impact-HTA Value Framework's value aspects took place in terms of their completeness for the purpose of value assessment (1a), together with feedback collection on the relevance of five suggested disease areas as topics for the case studies (1b), and feedback collection on relevant stakeholders to participate in the web-Delphi process(1c).

In the second Stage, a three-round web-Delphi process was designed to understand the relevance of the identified value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in five selected disease contexts or therapeutic areas with each HTA partner agency. Overall, a four-level qualitative scale was used to classify the relevance of the value aspects, ranging from Essential, to Influential, to Complementary, to Irrelevant (see definition of relevance scale levels in **Table 1**). In the first round of the web-Delphi

(6th – 25th of May 2020), participants anonymously suggested the addition of new value aspects, together with any other comments they wanted to share. In the second round (18th June – 13th of July 2020), participants classified each value aspect for its relevance across each of the five selected disease contexts using the relevance qualitative scale. In the third and final round (22nd July – 14th September 2020), participants classified each value aspect in light of Round’s 2 results (including the rest group’s judgements and comments); participants could also provide additional general feedback in terms of the overall process adopted and results produced. The relevance of the value aspects for five disease or therapeutic areas were elicited with each agency: TLV included the disease areas of 1) Malignant neoplasms metastases (ICD-10 code: O2D), and 2) Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: O8B), among others; similarly, INAMI included the therapeutic areas of 1) Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication) for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, and 2) Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, among others. Eventually, this stage generated five sets of classifications for the value aspects (in terms of their relevance for the evaluation of new medicines) corresponding to each of the five disease or therapeutic areas complete, with each HTA agency, i.e. a total of 10 classifications of value aspects’ relevance.

Table 1: Definition of relevance scale levels used

Value scale level	Description
Essential	<p>this aspect must be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it is not possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose);</p> <p>it is not possible to reach an evaluation recommendation without explicitly considering performance on this aspect.</p>

Influential	this aspect is highly desirable to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it could still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); the lack of favourable performance on this aspect could influence the decision in a detrimental way, as a desirable benefit may not be captured.
Complementary	this aspect is advantageous to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it would still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); favourable performance on this aspect could act supportively to complement the designated purpose of the medicine, i.e. "nice-to-have".
Irrelevant	this aspect does not necessarily need to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (evidence of the medicine's performance on it, does not influence if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose).

In the third Stage, interviews with HTA agency staff took place for bridging the web-Delphi results of Stage 2, with the case study applications of Stage 4. Two senior staff members of each HTA agency reviewed and validated (or amended) the results of the web-Delphi process, approved the selection of two disease indications to act as case study topics, and provided general feedback about the results and their web-Delphi experience. More precisely, the case study topics corresponded to two disease indications falling within two of the more generalised disease or therapeutic areas that had been explored as part of the web-Delphi process in Stage 2. The relevance information of the value aspects corresponding to the respective wider disease or therapeutic areas were used (i.e. 1 and 2, as described above).

In the fourth and final Stage, the framework was tested in practice using real case studies, following a two-step interactive value modelling process engaging a group of experts from each HTA agency that simulated evaluation committees. Initially, an online web-questionnaire survey was shared with the members of the HTA agency's committees for each of the two disease indications to collect their individual value judgements about the performance of a set of treatment options across a number

of clinical value aspects based on a summary of the available clinical evidence. Then, following the analysis of the web-questionnaire results, a decision conference was conducted for each of the two disease indications with each HTA agency's committee to develop a shared multicriteria value model and validate its outputs.

Testing with HTA committees (Stage 4): two-step interactive process using MACBETH

As part of the CVM approach adopted, Measuring Attractiveness by a Categorical Based Evaluation Technique (MACBETH) was used for the elicitation of participants' value preferences(3), as part of the two-step interactive process described above (see **Figure 2**). In more detail, in the first step a web-questionnaire collected participants' judgements about differences in value between treatment options and a comparator using the MACBETH scale. The web-questionnaire was delivered by the Welphi platform, 4.0(4). Following the individual judgements elicited in the web-questionnaire and using decision majority rules, group majority judgements about differences in value between the treatments and the comparator were then used as an input to generate a preliminary "prototype" value model for the disease indication of interest. This model consisted of a list of value aspects organised in a hierarchical tree structure, options' performance scores for each value aspect, and their relative weights.

In the second step of the virtual decision conferences, the preliminary "prototype" value model acted as the starting point to facilitate the group's discussion and develop a "shared" multicriteria value model, evaluating the incremental value of the treatments versus the comparator, and generate their respective overall weighted preference value (WPV) scores. The decision conference was guided by an impartial facilitator, expert in collaborative group processes, and the modelling aspects relating to assessment and appraisal were facilitated by the decision-support system WisedOn, implementing the MACBETH questioning protocol and algorithm(5). This two-step process was conducted for each case study, a total of four times (i.e. two disease indications with two HTA agencies). It should be highlighted that although the NSCLC case study was comprised only of clinical value aspects while leveraging preference information elicited both from the web-questionnaire and the decision conference (i.e. multicriteria model 1), the SMA case study was also comprised of non-clinical value aspects which only leveraged information elicited from the decision

conference (i.e. multicriteria model 2) (see case studies overview in **Figure 3**). The aim was to adopt a sequential approach for building a shared multi-criteria value model in two steps; first by focusing on the clinical value aspects only reflecting the treatments’ health outcome implications (Model 1), to estimate a multidimensional health outcome metric, while also considering treatment costs in an attempt to operationalise treatments’ efficiency value aspect (i.e. their value-for-money), without being restricted in a single health outcome metric only (e.g. Life Years or Quality Adjusted Life Years gained). Then, to enhance the model by incorporating other non-clinical value aspects reflecting the treatments’ non health outcome implications and their trade-offs (Model 2), in an attempt to estimate an overall multidimensional value metric. The generic clinical and non-clinical value aspects for the case of INAMI and TLV are illustrated in **Figure 4**.

Figure 2: Testing the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework with HTA committees (two-step interactive process)

Figure 3: Overview of NSCLC and SMA case studies

MCDA steps for NSCLC and SMA case study applications (Stage 4)

In total, four empirical applications took place in the form of case studies, one on Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC) and one on Spinal Muscular Atrophy (SMA), each one conducted in collaboration with the Swedish TLV and the Belgian INAMI-RIZIV. The MCDA methodological process adopted in terms of the design and reporting of the case studies is in alignment with ISPOR MCDA Good Practice Guidelines, mainly in regard to the validation of each step with relevant experts, stakeholders and decision-makers (see **Table 2**)(6). The use of the particular methods for scoring,

Figure 4: The generic clinical and non-clinical value aspects for INAMI (A) and TLV (B)

(A)

(B)

IMPACT TLV NSCLC model 1 GENERAL criado em 04/13/2021

▣ ▾ Clinical value aspects
▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
▣ Impact on morbidity (Influential)
▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)
▣ Adverse events profile (Complementary)
▣ Tolerability to patients (Complementary)
▣ Impact on health related quality of life (Essential)
▣ Impact on patient functionality (Complementary)
▣ Duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)(Complementary)
▣ Time for treatment effect (Influential)
▣ Value as a bridge therapy (Complementary)
▣ Risk of leakage across indications (Influential)
▣ ▾ Non-clinical value aspects
▣ Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)
▣ Size of patient population (e.g. rarity) (Complementary)
▣ Severity of the disease (Essential)
▣ Medicine's economic impact (Essential)
▣ Medicine's affordability (Influential)
▣ Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (Influential)
▣ Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary)
▣ Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (Complementary)
▣ Unmet need of the disease (Influential)
▣ Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (Irrelevant)
▣ Risk of leakage across indications (Complementary)
▣ Risk of drug addiction and its severity (Irrelevant)
▣ Medicine's efficiency (Essential)

Table 2: Adaptation of ISPOR MCDA Good Practice Guidelines in the NSCLC and SMA case studies

MCDA Step	Recommendation	Action
Defining the decision problem	Develop a clear description of the decision problem Validate and report the decision problem	Selection of disease indication and technologies in collaboration with HTA agency staff (Interviews)
Selecting and structuring criteria	Report and justify the methods used to identify criteria Report and justify the criteria definitions Validate and report the criteria and the value tree	Selection of value aspects in collaboration with HTA agency stakeholders (web-Delphi)
Measuring performance	Report and justify the sources used to measure performance	Clinical data and operationalisation of the respective value aspects using performance indicators (performance matrix) validated with clinical experts

	Validate and report the performance matrix	
Scoring alternatives	Report and justify the methods used for scoring Validate and report scores	Scoring on clinical value aspects initially informed by individual HTA evaluation committee members (web-questionnaire), then validated with the whole group (decision-conference); for non-clinical value aspects, only the latter
Weighting criteria	Report and justify the methods used for weighting Validate and report weights	Weighting of clinical value aspects initially informed by individual HTA evaluation committee members (web-questionnaire), then validated with the whole group (decision-conference); for non-clinical value aspects, only the latter
Calculating aggregate scores	Report and justify the aggregation function used Validate and report results of the aggregation	Aggregation of partial value scores and weights into overall weighted preference value scores validated with participants on the spot (decision conference)

<p>Dealing with uncertainty</p>	<p>Report sources of uncertainty Report and justify the uncertainty analysis</p>	<p>In terms of quality of clinical evidence, number of patients, follow up times, and treatment effects confidence intervals reported (performance matrix). In terms of parameter uncertainty (criteria, scores, weights), one-way sensitivity analysis on the spot (decision conference). In terms of further parameter and structural uncertainty, n-way sensitivity analysis in the weights of criteria (offline)</p>
<p>Reporting and examining of findings</p>	<p>Report the MCDA method and findings Examine the MCDA findings</p>	<p>Results transparently analysed and interpreted using tabular and graphical forms, in collaboration with participants (decision conference), with follow up reports shared</p>

weighting and aggregating, mainly using a combination of swing weighting matrices and MACBETH, was justified based on the objective of the research project and the relevant supporting literature (3, 7-12).

The selection of the disease indications and the technologies to be evaluated (i.e. decision problem definition) took place as part of the Interviews in Stage 3 described above, in collaboration with TLV and INAMI staff, resulting into an agreement to focus on second line NSMLC and symptomatic SMA type 1. The selection of generically relevant value aspects (i.e. evaluation criteria) initially took place in collaboration with TLV and INAMI stakeholders as part of the web-Delphi process in Stage 2 described above. Clinical data were then validated with clinical experts specialising in the respective disease areas, using performance matrices for the alternative treatments evaluated leveraging the best available evidence, together with the operationalisation of the general value aspects into disease specific value attributes corresponding to performance indicators in the study.

The data collected for the two case study topics, validated with each clinical expert, corresponding to the respective performance matrices of the final selected value aspects to be used for the NSCLC and SMA case studies are shown in **Tables 3 – 4**. The scoring of the alternative treatments and the weighting of the clinical value aspects was informed by the participants comprising the evaluation committees, initially as part of the first step of the interactive process corresponding to the web-questionnaire, as described above. This generated a preliminary “prototype” clinical value model, which then acted as the starting point for the discussions in the decision conferences. Initially, the decision conferences kicked off with a presentation by the collaborating clinical experts, giving an overview of the disease area and indication, with a summary of treatment pathways in place and clinical evidence available for the interventions evaluated in the case studies. The selection of the value aspects/performance indicators, together with the scoring and weighting were then validated by seeking group consensus or agreement, using the MACBETH questioning protocol, scale and algorithm; in cases where agreement could not be reached (in terms of scoring or weighting), majority voting was used, and the respective MACBETH value judgements were eventually explored in sensitivity analysis. For the case of non-clinical value aspects (SMA only), scoring and weighting took place directly in the decision conference. The treatments’ partial preference value scores and the respective criteria relative weights were then combined into overall weighted preference value

Table 3: Performance matrix of final value aspects in NSCLC case study

Clinical studies		CheckMate 057	CheckMate 057	CheckMate 017	CheckMate 017	Keynote- Keynote-010	Keynote- 010	OAK	OAK
Value aspect	Performance indicator	Nivolumab	Docetaxel	Nivolumab	Docetaxel	Pembrolizumab	Docetaxel	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
Medicine's impact on mortality	Median OS, months	11.1	8.1	11.1	8.1	11.8	8.4	13.8	9.6
Medicine's impact on mortality	Median OS, range	9.2 - 13.1	7.2 - 9.2	9.2 - 13.1	7.2 - 9.2	10.4 - 13.1	7.6 - 9.5	11.8-15.7	8.6-11.2
Medicine's impact on mortality	OS, hazard ratio	0.68	-	0.68	-	0.69	-	0.75	-

Medicine's impact on mortality	OS, hazard ratio range	0.59 - 0.78	-	0.59 - 0.78	-	0.60 - 0.80	-	0.64 - 0.89	-
Medicine's impact on mortality	OS, p-value	NR	-	NR	-	p<0.00001	-	p=0.0006	-
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Objective response, %	20%	11%	20%	11%	18%	9%	15%	13%
Medicine's adverse events profile	Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 adverse events, %	10%	55%	10%	55%	15.4%	35%	14.9%	42.4%
Medicine's adverse events profile	Patients with Adverse events leading to	6%	13%	6%	13%	5.9%	12.0%	7.9%	18.3%

	withdrawal from treatment, %								
Duration of treatment effect	Duration of response, median, months	19.9	5.6	19.9	5.6	not reached	6	16.3	6.2
Duration of treatment effect	Duration of response, median, range	11.4 - 30.8	4.4 - 7.0	11.4 - 30.8	4.4 - 7.0	4.2 - 10.5	2.7 - 6.1	10.0 - (not estimable)	4.9 - 7.6

Table 4: Performance matrix of final value aspects in SMA case study

Clinical studies		STR1VE US	STR1VE EU	STR1VE EU/US combined data	ENDEAR	ENDEAR	FIREFISH Part 2
Value aspect	Performance indicator	Zolgensma			Spinraza	Best Supportive Care	Evrysdi
Medicine's impact on mortality	Event-free survival, % of patients	91%	94%	93%	61%	32%	85%
Medicine's impact on morbidity	Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %	64%	19%	37%	10%*	0%*	29%

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Medicine's impact on morbidity	Patients able to feed orally and did not require nutritional support, %	86%	67%	75%	25%*	0%*	74%
Medicine's adverse events profile	% of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)	41%	55%	49%	60%	56%	51%
Medicine's tolerability to patients	% of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation	9%	NR	9%	16%	39%	0%
Delivery system and posology	Combination of the delivery system and the posology (i.e. dosing)	One-time IV infusion (reduced complexity)			Intrathecally; an induction period (4 loading doses) is followed by life-long repeated intrathecal administrations every 4 months	N/A	Administered orally once daily

Mechanism of action	The technology's mechanism of action	Recombinant AAV9-based gene therapy designed to deliver a copy of the gene encoding the human SMN protein.	Antisense oligonucleotide (ASO) designed to treat SMA caused by mutations in chromosome 5q that lead to SMN protein deficiency	N/A	Survival of motor neuron 2 (SMN2) splicing modifier designed to treat patients with SMA caused by mutations in chromosome 5q that lead to SMN protein deficiency.
Need for specialised hospital setting	Need for specialised hospital setting	Provided at high specialist centres. Before administration of onasemnogene abeparvovec, baseline laboratory testing is required, including: AAV9 antibody testing using an appropriately validated assay, liver function: alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and total bilirubin, platelet count, and troponin-I.	Offered primarily at academic medical center. At baseline and prior to each dose, obtain a platelet count, coagulation laboratory testing, and quantitative	N/A	Administered at-home

			spot urine protein testing		
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*indicates clinical expert judgement

(WPV) scores, through linear additive aggregation (i.e. weighted average estimation), which were validated with the decision conference participants on the spot. In terms of dealing with uncertainty, in order for participants to consider quality of the clinical evidence used, the performance matrices reported the number of patients from the respective clinical studies, together with the follow up times (i.e. study durations) and the confidence intervals of the treatment effects. In terms of parameter uncertainty relating to the inclusion of specific value aspects, treatments' scores, and criteria weights, sensitivity analysis was conducted at the end of the decision conference on judgements for which there was disagreement. Finally, in terms of reporting and examining the findings, the results were transparently analysed and interpreted in collaboration with decision conference participants, with follow up reports being shared with them, supported by various tabular and graphical formats. All the above MCDA model building, assessment and appraisal steps were facilitated by the decision support system WisedOn, implementing the MACBETH value scale and algorithm to automatically calculate overall WPV scores, and offering sensitivity analysis features, while presenting the results in different tabular and graphical formats.

Results

Web-Delphi process, generic list of value aspects and their relevance across decision contexts (Stages 2-3)

A total of 36 invitations were sent to INAMI stakeholders to participate in the web-Delphi, out of which 17 completed the first round, 14 the second round, and 13 the third round. For TLV stakeholders, out of 11 invitations sent, 9 completed the first round, 8 the second round, and 6 the third round (see **Table 5**).

Following the first round of the web-Delphi process, earlier (web-Delphi) findings of the project on relevant value aspects for HTA stakeholders at international level (Task 2) were validated and supplemented with INAMI and TLV stakeholders to generate HTA agency-specific lists of generic value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in their own countries (see **Table 6**). A preliminary generic list of 20 value aspects was supplemented with 3 additional aspects for INAMI, and 4 additional aspects for TLV, giving a total of 23 and 24 value aspects respectively, acting as the final lists.

For the first two decision contexts (capturing the case studies' disease indication topics), the relevance classifications of the final value aspects are shown in **Tables 7-8** for INAMI and **Tables 9-10** for TLV, respectively. In terms of the first decision context (i.e. indication expansion in severe disease with a number of treatments available for INAMI, malignant neoplasm metastases for TLV), 12 value aspects were classified as "Essential", 3 as "Influential", and 8 as "Complementary" for INAMI; no value aspect was judged to be "Irrelevant" (**Table 7**). For the case of TLV, 5 value aspects were classified as "Essential", 7 as "Influential", 10 as "Complementary" and 2 as "Irrelevant" for TLV (**Table 9**).

When focusing on the second decision context (i.e. life threatening orphan disease with few symptomatic treatments and entry of new advanced therapy for INAMI, or motor neuron diseases and related disorders for TLV), 11 value aspects were classified as "Essential", 6 as "Influential", and 6 as "Complementary" for INAMI; again, no value aspect was judged to be "Irrelevant" (**Table 8**). For the case of TLV, 8 value aspects were classified as "Essential", 7 as "Influential", 7 as "Complementary" and 2 as "Irrelevant" for TLV (**Table 10**).

Table 5: Numbers of web-Delphi responders per stakeholder group between agencies

Web-Delphi Round	TLV (total invitations = 11)			INAMI (total invitations = 36)		
	R1	R2	R3	R1	R2	R3
Health care professionals, e.g. clinicians, pharmacists, etc.				5	3	3
HTA bodies, e.g. HTA committees, evidence assessors, etc.	5	5	4	5	5	5
Industry, e.g. pharmaceutical companies, industry associations, etc.				3	2	1
Payers and policy-makers, e.g. ministry of health, local/central government, etc.	1	1		2	2	2
General population, e.g. tax payers, citizen representatives, etc.				1	1	1
Scientific experts and methodologists, e.g. epidemiologists, health economists, etc.	3	2	2			
Patients and carers, e.g. patient organisations, patient advocates/ carers, etc.						
Other				1	1	1
TOTAL	9	8	6	17	14	13

Table 6: Generic list of relevant value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines with TLV and INAMI following web-Delphi first round results (Stage 2)

HTA agency relevance	Value aspects	Description
TLV and INAMI	A - Severity of the disease	The condition's/ indication's degree of seriousness in respect to mortality and morbidity.
TLV and INAMI	B - Unmet need of the disease	The availability of effective medical interventions for the indication of interest, which could relate to methods of diagnosis, prevention or treatment.
TLV and INAMI	C - Medicine's impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.
TLV and INAMI	D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease).
TLV and INAMI	E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.
TLV and INAMI	F - Medicine's adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.
TLV and INAMI	G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.

TLV and INAMI	H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration instructions, e.g. oral pill vs intravenous solution.
TLV and INAMI	I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Any risk reduction in transmitting and developing the disease under consideration or any other disease within the broader population.
TLV and INAMI	J - Medicine's economic impact	Impact of medicine's adoption in terms of overall magnitude of economic losses and gains and their distribution across direct (health and non-health related) costs and indirect (i.e. productivity loss) costs.
TLV and INAMI	K - Medicine's affordability	Impact of the medicine's adoption on financial resources by taking into account the prevalence of the disease at the whole patient population, e.g. budget impact.
TLV and INAMI	L - Medicine's efficiency	The medicine's value-for-money in terms of resource allocation, e.g. the additional cost needed to gain an extra unit of health outcome, i.e. Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio.
TLV and INAMI	M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the pivotal clinical studies used that can cause the effect of the medicine to be overestimated or underestimated due to a number of biases, e.g. selection bias due to non-randomised sequence generation, performance bias due to ineffective blinding of participants and personnel, detection bias due to

		ineffective blinding of outcome assessment, attrition bias due to incomplete outcome data, reporting bias due to selective reporting, etc.
TLV and INAMI	N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).
TLV and INAMI	O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	The possible inequities arising from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine including those associated with gender, age, race, disability and/or socioeconomic status and the need to subscribe to solidarity and human dignity.
TLV and INAMI	P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	The potential of the medicine to act as a "bridge therapy" by keeping the patient alive so that they can benefit from better treatment options, e.g. until bone marrow transplant or development of future technologies.
TLV and INAMI	Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	Impact of the medicine on the ability of patient to function socially in a variety of activities (as implied by improvements in functionality).
TLV and INAMI	R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	Time for the medicine's treatment effect to take place (e.g. fast drug action vs slow drug action).

TLV and INAMI	S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration).
TLV and INAMI	T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	The degree of reversibility (or irreversibility) of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (e.g. reversible adverse effects vs irreversible adverse effects).
TLV	U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	The condition's/ indication's prevalence in terms of whether it fulfills rarity (<1 in 10,000) or ultra-rarity (<1 in 50,000) thresholds.
TLV	V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	Risk of leakage across patient sub-groups that have not been recommended for reimbursement (e.g. above/below a specific age).
TLV	W - Risk of leakage across indications	Risk of off-label use (e.g. use of bevacizumab for AMD or testosterone replacement therapy in the absence of clinical diagnosis of hypogonadism).
TLV	X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	The extent to which a drug creates a propensity/ urge to continue using it despite adverse consequences and the severity of these adverse consequences.
INAMI	U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Number of cases of the disease at present or number of new cases that develop, e.g. prevalence of the disease (i.e. proportion of a population that have the disease at a point in time) or incidence of the disease (i.e. rate at which new disease cases occur in a population during a specified period).

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INAMI	V - Medicine's spill-over effects	R&D positive externalities (i.e. beneficial follow-on external effects) that can lead to subsequent innovation in the form of new medicines or new indications, e.g. number of follow-on medicines (i.e. subsequent class entrants) approved, or number of additional indications investigated in phase 3 trials.
INAMI	W - Medicine's mechanism of action	The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).

Table 7: INAMI value aspects relevance classification for Disease Context 1

1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.	
Relevance level	Value aspects
Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A - Severity of the disease B - Unmet need of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality D - Medicine's impact on morbidity E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life F - Medicine's adverse events profile G - Medicine's tolerability to patients J - Medicine's economic impact K - Medicine's affordability L - Medicine's efficiency M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

Complementary	I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality R - Medicine's time for treatment effect U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity) V - Medicine's spill-over effects W - Medicine's mechanism of action
Irrelevant	n/a

Table 8: INAMI value aspects relevance classification for Disease Context 2

2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.	
Relevance level	Value aspects
Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A - Severity of the disease B - Unmet need of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality D - Medicine's impact on morbidity E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life F - Medicine's adverse events profile J - Medicine's economic impact K - Medicine's affordability L - Medicine's efficiency S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s) U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> G - Medicine's tolerability to patients M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality R - Medicine's time for treatment effect T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

Complementary	H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy V - Medicine's spill-over effects W - Medicine's mechanism of action
Irrelevant	n/a

Table 9: TLV value aspects relevance classification for Disease Context 1

1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: 02D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.	
Relevance level	Value aspects
Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A - Severity of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life J - Medicine's economic impact L - Medicine's efficiency
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> B - Unmet need of the disease D - Medicine's impact on morbidity K - Medicine's affordability M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials R - Medicine's time for treatment effect S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s) W - Risk of leakage across indications
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F - Medicine's adverse events profile G - Medicine's tolerability to patients H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity) V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication

Irrelevant	I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity
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Table 10: TLV value aspects relevance classification for Disease Context 2

2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B), e.g. spinal muscular atrophy.	
Relevance level	Value aspects
Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A - Severity of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality D - Medicine's impact on morbidity E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life L - Medicine's efficiency Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity) V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> B - Unmet need of the disease J - Medicine's economic impact K - Medicine's affordability M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials R - Medicine's time for treatment effect S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s) W - Risk of leakage across indications
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F - Medicine's adverse events profile G - Medicine's tolerability to patients H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

Irrelevant	I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity
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As a result, it becomes evident that different value aspects matter to a different degree across different disease and therapeutic areas and between HTA agencies. Considering the first decision context with TLV which generated the smallest number of value aspects as “Essential” (n = 5), these were Severity of disease (A), Medicine’s impact on mortality (C), Medicine’s impact on health-related quality of life (E), Medicine’s economic impact (J), and Medicine’s efficiency (L). With the exception of 1 value aspect (Medicine’s economic impact), the rest value aspects were also classified as “Essential” in the second decision context with TLV, together with an additional 4 aspects (n =8). Furthermore, the same 5 value aspects were also classified as “Essential” in both decision contexts with INAMI, supplemented with another 7 and 6 value aspects in the first and second disease contexts respectively (n = 12; n = 11), indicating that their importance possibly holds across settings.

On a different front, when comparing the two HTA agencies’ classifications, it becomes evident that TLV is stricter with what they might be willing to consider “Essential” in their evaluations (n = 5; n = 8), compared to INAMI which could consider a larger number of value aspects as “Essential” (n = 12; n = 11). Similarly, INAMI considered no value aspect to be “Irrelevant” in either decision context, in contrast to TLV which classified the same two value aspects to be “Irrelevant” in both disease contexts; however, it should be noted that these value aspects were TLV-specific (added only by them), corresponding to Medicine’s impact on wider health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (I), and Risk of drug addiction and its severity (X).

The most substantial (proportional) change differences between the decision contexts within the same HTA agency took place for the value aspects classified as “Influential” with INAMI (n = 3 vs 6), followed by the value aspects classified as “Essential” with TLV (n = 5 vs 8). In terms of the “Complementary” classification, TLV judged a larger number of such value aspects in both contexts (n = 10; n = 7) compared to INAMI (n = 8; n = 6).

After combining the “Essential” and “Influential” value aspects together in a “high relevance” category and the “Complementary” and “Irrelevant” value aspects together in a “low relevance” category, a total of 15 “high relevance” value aspects and 8 “low relevance” value aspects were

generated from INAMI in the first decision context, vs 12 and 12 from TLV respectively. Similarly, a total of 17 “high relevance” value aspects and 6 “low relevance” value aspects were generated from INAMI in the second decision context, vs 15 and 9 from TLV, indicating a larger number of “high relevance” value aspects with INAMI compared to TLV, and a larger number of “low relevance” value aspects with TLV compared to INAMI, in both decision contexts. The relevance classifications of the value aspects for the rest decision contexts corresponding to the remaining disease areas or therapeutic areas, are shown in the **Supplementary Material**.

NSCLC case study with INAMI and TLV (Stage 4)

The two-step interactive process for the NSCLC case study initially involved a web-questionnaire (February 26th - March 2nd for INAMI, April 12th - 16th for TLV) to collect individual value judgments about the performance of the three immunotherapy treatments of interest (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), on five clinical value aspects. Nine INAMI and five TLV participants expressed separately their individual value judgements, with group majority judgements being derived from them, based on which the prototype multicriteria value model was built.

The top-half of **Table 11** summarises the NSCLC clinical value aspects and performance indicators used in the first step of the web-questionnaire; the bottom half of **Table 11** summarises the justification for excluding the rest clinical value aspects; for any of the value aspects from **Table 6** not listed, it means they were classified as non-clinical aspects and therefore were not included in the preliminary web-questionnaire (only considered for the decision conference of the SMA case study). The evidence summary for the selected clinical value aspects of interest shared with the participants of the web-questionnaires, their individual MACBETH judgements’, their respective MACBETH group judgements based on decision majority rules, and their conversion into treatment value scores using the MACBETH algorithm, are shown in the **Supplementary Material**.

Table 11: Selected clinical NSCLC value aspects and their respective performance indicators used in the web-questionnaire of the two-step interactive process (top-half); excluded clinical value aspects and its justification (bottom-half).

Value aspects name	Value aspects description	Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.	Median Overall Survival (OS), months Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease).	Objective response (i.e. best overall response)
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration).	Median duration of response, months
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.	Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 Adverse Events (AEs), %
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.	Patients with Adverse Events (AEs) leading to treatment withdrawal, %
Value aspects name	Value aspects description	Exclusion justification

Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.	No adequate data available.
Medicines' impact on patient functionality	Impact of the medicine on the ability of patient to function socially in a variety of activities (as implied by improvements in functionality).	No adequate data available. This aspect would most probably be partially captured/addressed by the combination of the rest value aspects in model 1.
Medicine's time for treatment effect	Time for the medicine's treatment effect to take place (e.g. fast drug action vs slow drug action).	No adequate data available. This aspect would not be fully relevant for this therapeutic area.
Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	The potential of the medicine to act as a "bridge therapy" by keeping the patient alive so that they can benefit from better treatment options, e.g. until bone marrow transplant or development of future technologies.	No adequate data available. This aspect would not be fully relevant for this disease indication. This aspect would most probably be partially captured/addressed by the mortality aspect.
Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	The degree of reversibility (or irreversibility) of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (e.g. reversible adverse effects vs irreversible adverse effects).	No adequate data available. Given the similar type of technologies, treatments would probably have an equal performance.

Tables 12 and 13 summarise the results of the prototype NSCLC models with INAMI and TLV respectively, including the overall WPV scores of each treatment option, treatments' performance value scores across the value aspects, and their relative weights. In both cases, the treatments' ranking was the same, with Nivolumab at the top, followed by Pembrolizumab, Atezolizumab and Docetaxel. For the case of INAMI, Adverse events profile had the highest relative weight (28%) followed by Duration of treatment (22%), and then the rest three value aspects at equal weight (17%). For the case of TLV, all value aspects corresponded to an equal weight (20%).

Following the first web-questionnaire step, an online decision conference took place (March 4th for INAMI with 10 participants, April 19th for TLV with 5 participants) to develop a shared multicriteria model and discuss its outputs, therefore enhancing the prototype model. **Tables 14 and 15** summarise the results of the final NSCLC models with INAMI and TLV respectively. Compared to the prototype model, treatments' ranking based on the final results following the INAMI decision conference was changed, with Atezolizumab becoming second and Pembrolizumab dropping to third. This was due to a change in the MACBETH value judgements used for scoring and weighting. Although differences also existed in the group's value judgements following the TLV decision conference, any emerging changes in value scores and weights did not cause a change in the treatment's ranking. Overall, differences existed in the final rankings between the two agencies, with Atezolizumab being ranked second followed by Pembrolizumab third in the case of INAMI, and vice versa for the case of TLV; with both agencies, Nivolumab ranked first, with docetaxel being last.

Figures 5 and 6 illustrate histograms corresponding to the final relative weights of the NSCLC value aspects, showing respectively the INAMI and TLV decision conference groups' MACBETH value judgements which were used as inputs for conversion into numerical weights. For the case of INAMI, more than 1/3 of the model's total weight corresponded to the Adverse events profile (36.3%), with about 1/4 of the model's total weight corresponding to Duration of treatment effect(s) (22.7%), and then an equal weight for Impact of mortality, Impact on morbidity and Tolerability to patients (13.6%). For the case of TLV, just over 1/3 of the model's weight corresponded to Impact on mortality (34.4%), with 1/4 corresponding to Duration of treatment effect(s) (25%), just over 1/5 corresponding to Impact on morbidity (21.8%), 1/8 to Adverse events profile (12.5%) and less than 1/10 to Tolerability to patients (6.2%).

Table 12: INAMI results of the preliminary prototype NSCLC model

			Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
Clinical Value Aspects	INAMI relevance	Weights	100	79.17	66.67	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	17%	100	100	75	0
Impact on morbidity	Essential	17%	100	75	25	0
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Essential	22%	100	50	75	0
Adverse events profile	Essential	28%	100	80	60	0
Tolerability to patients	Essential	17%	100	100	100	0

Table 13: TLV results of the preliminary prototype NSCLC model

			Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
Clinical Value Aspects	TLV relevance	Weights	95	80	75	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	20%	75	100	100	0
Impact on morbidity	Influential	20%	100	75	50	0
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Influential	20%	100	50	75	0
Adverse events profile	Complementary	20%	100	75	75	0
Tolerability to patients	Complementary	20%	100	100	75	0

Table 14: INAMI results of the final decision conference NSCLC model

			Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
Clinical Value Aspects	INAMI relevance	Weights	100	64.77	67.61	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	14%	100	100	100	0
Impact on morbidity	Essential	14%	100	100	25	0
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Essential	23%	100	25	62.5	0
Adverse events profile	Essential	36%	100	50	62.5	0
Tolerability to patients	Essential	14%	100	100	100	0

Table 15: TLV results of the final decision conference NSCLC model

			Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
Clinical Value Aspects	TLV relevance	Weights	97.5	60.63	52.03	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	34%	100	100	75	0
Impact on morbidity	Influential	25%	100	60	20	0
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Influential	22%	100	12.5	37.5	0
Adverse events profile	Complementary	13%	100	50	50	0
Tolerability to patients	Complementary	6%	60	60	100	0

Figure 5: Histogram with the final relative weights of NSCLC value aspects, following the INAMI decision conference

Figure 6: Histogram with the final relative weights of the NSCLC value aspects, following the TLV decision conference

Figures 7 and 8 summarise the NSCLC treatments' profiles resulting from the INAMI and TLV decision conferences respectively, corresponding to the partial weighted value scores of each treatment across the five clinical value aspects. For the case of INAMI, the top ranked option (Nivolumab) had equal performance with one of the options in one instance (Impact on morbidity) equal performance with both of the other two options in two instances (Impact on mortality, Tolerability to patients), and superior performance to both options in another two instances (Duration of treatment effects, Adverse events profile). For the case of TLV, the top ranked option (Nivolumab) had inferior performance in one instance (Tolerability to patients), equal performance with one of the options in once instance (Impact on mortality), and superior performance to both options in three instances (Impact on morbidity, Duration of treatment effects, Adverse events profile). A more detailed comparison of the preliminary prototype models versus the final decision conference models with INAMI and TLV are shown in the **Supplementary Material**. Finally, a sensitivity analysis focusing on the difference in value between Adverse events profile and Duration of treatment effect(s) (from moderate to very strong) revealed no significant changes on the added value of the treatments in the INAMI case study. In order for the ranking of the treatments to be changed, the relative weight of the Adverse event profile would have to decrease substantially from 36% to 15%.

SMA case study with INAMI and TLV (Stage 4)

The two-step interactive process for the SMA case study initially involved a web-questionnaire (March 26th – 30th for INAMI, April 12th - 16th for TLV) to collect individual value judgments about the performance of the treatments of interest (Zolgensma, Spinraza, and Evrysdi), relative to Best Supportive Care (BSC), on four or five clinical value aspects. Eight INAMI and six TLV participants expressed separately their individual value judgements, with group majority judgements being derived from them, based on which the prototype multicriteria value model 1 was built.

Figure 7: Comparison of NSCLC treatments' profiles, following the INAMI decision conference

Figure 8: Comparison of NSCLC treatments' profiles, following the TLV decision conference

The top-half of **Table 16** summarises the SMA clinical value aspects and performance indicators used in the first step of the web-questionnaire (in either of the two agencies); the bottom half of **Table 16** summarises the justification for excluding the rest clinical value aspects; for any of the value aspects from **Table 6** not listed, it means they were classified as non-clinical aspects and therefore were not included in the preliminary web-questionnaire (some considered for the decision conference). It should be highlighted that during the decision conference with INAMI, the Adverse events profile value aspect was eliminated since participants considered there was no difference in judgements between the treatments and the comparator, a new Health Related Quality of Life value aspect was added (which was used for the web-questionnaire of TLV), and the indicator of Tolerability to patients was modified; **Table 16** incorporates these amendments.

The evidence summary for the selected clinical value aspects of interest shared with the participants of the web-questionnaires, their individual MACBETH judgements', their respective MACBETH group judgements based on decision majority rules, and their conversion into treatment value scores using the MACBETH algorithm, are shown in the **Supplementary Material**.

Tables 17 and 18 summarise the results of the prototype SMA models with INAMI and TLV respectively, including the overall WPV scores of each treatment option, treatments' performance value scores across the value aspects, and their relative weights. Interestingly, the treatments' ranking was different between HTA agencies, with Evrysdi at the top, followed by Zolgensma, Spinraza and BSC at the bottom for the case of INAMI; for the case of TLV, Zolgensma ranked at the top, followed by Spinraza, Evrysdi, and BSC at the bottom.

Impact on mortality had the highest relative weight with both agencies (33%). For the case of INAMI, it was followed equally by Impact on morbidity and Tolerability to patients (27%), and then by Adverse events profile (13%). For the case of TLV, second-weighted aspect was Health Related Quality of Life (27% - not considered in INAMI web-questionnaire because it's indicator was only emerged during the latter's decision conference), followed by Impact on morbidity (20%), Tolerability to patients (13%), and Adverse events profile (7%).

Following the first web-questionnaire step, a virtual decision conference took place (March 31st for INAMI with 8 participants, April 20th for TLV with 5 participants) to develop a shared multicriteria model and discuss its outputs, therefore enhancing again the preliminary prototype model. **Tables 19 and 20** summarise the results of the final SMA clinical value models (model 1, clinical aspects

Table 16: Selected clinical SMA value aspects and their respective performance indicators used in the web-questionnaire of the two-step interactive process (top-half); excluded clinical value aspects and its justification (bottom-half).

Value aspects name	Value aspects description	Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.	Event-free survival, % of patients
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease).	Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %
Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life*	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.	Patients able to feed orally without nutritional support, %
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.	% of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.	% of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation
Value aspects name	Value aspects description	Exclusion justification
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration).	No adequate data available. This aspect would most probably be partially captured/addressed by the mortality aspect.
Medicines' impact on patient functionality	Impact of the medicine on the ability of patient to function socially in a variety of activities (as implied by improvements in functionality).	No adequate data available. This aspect would most probably be partially captured/addressed by the combination of the rest value aspects in model 1.

Medicine's time for treatment effect	Time for the medicine's treatment effect to take place (e.g. fast drug action vs slow drug action).	No adequate data available. This aspect would not be fully relevant for this therapeutic area.
Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	The potential of the medicine to act as a "bridge therapy" by keeping the patient alive so that they can benefit from better treatment options, e.g. until bone marrow transplant or development of future technologies.	No adequate data available. This aspect would not be fully relevant for this disease indication. This aspect would most probably be partially captured/addressed by the mortality aspect.
Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	The degree of reversibility (or irreversibility) of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (e.g. reversible adverse effects vs irreversible adverse effects).	No adequate data available. Given the similar type of technologies, treatments would probably have an equal performance.

*used only in the TLV web-questionnaire

Table 17: INAMI results of the preliminary prototype SMA model

			Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
Clinical Value Aspects	INAMI relevance	Weights	94.67	49.33	100	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	33%	100	80	100	0
Impact on morbidity	Essential	27%	100	75	100	0
Adverse events profile	Essential	13%	100	(-)100	100	0
Tolerability to patients	Influential	27%	80	60	100	0

Table 18: TLV results of the preliminary prototype SMA model

			Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
Clinical Value Aspects	TLV relevance	Weights	93.33	86.67	80	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	33%	100	80	60	0
Impact on morbidity	Essential	20%	100	66.67	100	0
Health Related Quality of Life	Essential	27%	75	100	75	0
Adverse events profile	Complementary	7%	100	100	100	0
Tolerability to patients	Complementary	13%	100	100	100	0

Table 19: INAMI results of the final decision conference SMA clinical value model 1

			Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
Clinical Value Aspects	INAMI relevance	Weights	90	63.22	100	0
Health Related Quality of Life	Essential	25%	100	42.86	100	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	36%	100	85	100	0
Impact on morbidity	Essential	14%	100	50	100	0
Tolerability to patients	Influential	25%	60	60	100	0

Table 20: TLV results of the final decision conference SMA clinical value model 1

			Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
Clinical Value Aspects	TLV relevance	Weights	97.56	38.66	90.85	0
Impact on mortality	Essential	29%	100	55	87.5	0
Impact on morbidity	Essential	22%	100	37.5	75	0
Health Related Quality of Life	Essential	32%	100	37.5	100	0
Adverse events profile	Complementary	5%	100	(-)100	100	0
Tolerability to patients	Complementary	12%	80	60	100	0

only) with INAMI and TLV respectively. Although differences existed in the group's value judgements following the INAMI decision conference, any emerging changes in value scores and weights did not result in a difference in the treatment's ranking. For the case of TLV, compared to the prototype model, treatments' ranking based on the final results following the decision conference was changed, with Evrysdi becoming second and Spinraza dropping to third. Overall, differences existed in the final (clinical) rankings between the two agencies, with Evrysdi being ranked first followed by Zolgensma in the case of INAMI, and vice versa for the case of TLV; with both agencies, Spinraza ranked third, followed by BSC.

Figures 9 and 10 illustrate histograms corresponding to the final relative weights of the SMA clinical value aspects (model 1), showing respectively the INAMI and TLV decision conference groups' MACBETH value judgements which were used as inputs for conversion into numerical weights. For the case of INAMI, more than 1/3 of the model's total weight corresponded to the Impact on mortality (35.7%), with an identical weight equal to 1/4 of the model's total corresponding to Tolerability to patients (25%) and Health Related Quality of Life (25%), and then Impact on morbidity (14.3%). For the case of TLV, just under 1/3 of the model's weight corresponded to Health Related Quality of Life (31.7%), and Impact on mortality (29.3%), with just over 1/5 corresponding to Impact on morbidity (22%), about 1/8 to Tolerability to patients (12.2%) and almost 1/20 to Tolerability to patients (4.9%).

Figures 11 and 12 summarise the SMA treatments' clinical profiles resulting from the INAMI and TLV decision conferences respectively, corresponding to the partial value scores of each treatment across the four or five clinical value aspects of model 1. For the case of INAMI, the top ranked option was Evrysdi which had equal performance with the second ranked option in three instances (Impact on mortality, Health related quality of life, Impact on morbidity), and superior performance to both options in another instance (Tolerability to patients). For the case of TLV, the top ranked option was instead Zolgensma which had inferior performance in one instance (Tolerability to patients), equal performance with both or one of the options in two instances (Adverse events profile, Duration of treatment effects), and superior performance to both options in two instances (Impact on morbidity, Impact on morbidity). A more detailed comparison of the preliminary prototype models versus the final decision conference models with INAMI and TLV are shown in the **Supplementary Material**.

Figure 9: Histogram with the final relative weights of SMA clinical value aspects (model 1), following the INAMI decision conference

Figure 10: Histogram with the final relative weights of SMA clinical value aspects (model 1), following the TLV decision conference

Figure 11: Comparison of SMA treatments’ clinical profiles, following the INAMI decision conference

Figure 12: Comparison of SMA treatments’ clinical profiles, following the TLV decision conference

Finally, **Tables 21 and 22** summarise the results of the final SMA non-clinical value models (model 2, non-clinical value aspects only) with INAMI and TLV respectively. For the case of INAMI, it becomes evident that instead of Evrysdi which was the top-ranked option in terms of clinical value aspects, Zolgensma is the top-ranked option in terms of non-clinical value aspects, followed by Evrysdi and then by Spinraza. For the case of TLV, Zolgensma was also the top-ranked option in terms of non-clinical value aspects, having the same ranking with clinical value aspects. It should be noted that compared to model 1 where the evaluations and rankings took place incrementally to the value of a comparator option (i.e. BSC), in model 2 the evaluations and rankings took place directly among the three alternative options of interest only, without the inclusion of a comparator as a benchmark (given its irrelevance in non-clinical performance).

Figures 13 and 14 are plots illustrating a comparison of treatments' added clinical value scores (versus BSC) compared to treatments' non-clinical value scores, for INAMI and TLV respectively. These plots illustrate the findings described above in a different visual way; first they showcase that in the case of INAMI one option was ranked best in terms of clinical value aspects (Evrysdi, model 1) and a different option was ranked best in terms of non-clinical value aspects (Zolgensma, model 2). For the case of TLV, the same option was ranked first both in terms of clinical and non-clinical value aspects (Zolgensma, models 1 and 2).

Table 21: INAMI results of the final decision conference SMA non-clinical value model 2

			Zolgensma	Evrysdi	Spinraza
Non-clinical Value Aspects	INAMI relevance	Weights	91.67	60	0
Ease and convenience for patients	Complementary	70%	100	50	0
Mechanism of action	Complementary	25%	100	0	0
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	Influential	5%	66.67	100	0

Table 22: TLV results of the final decision conference SMA non-clinical value model 2

			Zolgensma	Evrysdi	Spinraza
Non-clinical Value Aspects	TLV relevance	Weights	92.73	60.23	0
Ease and convenience for patients	Complementary	64%	100	37.5	0
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	Complementary	36%	80	100	0

Figure 13: X-Y plot of SMA treatments' added clinical value scores (versus BSC) compared to treatments' non-clinical value scores, for INAMI

Figure 14: X-Y plot of SMA treatments' added clinical value scores (versus BSC) compared to treatments' non-clinical value scores, for TLV

Policy implications

This section of the deliverable brings together the policy implications from Tasks 2 and 3 of this work package.

Our research demonstrates a number of important findings relating to the value preferences underlying the evaluation of new medicines by HTA agencies and the prospects in developing more structured and flexible methodologies.

First, the results indicate that what matters in the evaluation of new medicines from the perspective of HTA agencies is not limited to their clinical benefits in terms of mortality and morbidity, e.g. in terms of Life Years or Quality Adjusted Life Years gained, and costs. The value of new medicines seems to represent a much more comprehensive concept, which could operationally be captured by a number of clinical and non-clinical value aspects. This concept of value becomes even more complex given that its components vary across different decision contexts; as part of different disease and therapeutic areas, what is judged to be relevant for the evaluation of new medicines does not remain constant, even when the judgements are provided by the same members of HTA institutions (simulating HTA appraisal and payer evaluation committees). Furthermore, there are different degrees of value aspects' relevance, characterizing their relative importance to the evaluation, which also vary between decision contexts. Therefore, what matters relatively more or less in the evaluation of a set of medicines for a particular disease indication, is likely to vary compared to another set of medicines targeting a different indication. These findings apply both in terms of evaluation within the same agencies or committees, but also between them. In other words, differences in terms of the relevance of value aspects in the evaluation, and their relative importance, seem to vary across different disease contexts both within and across institutions. Therefore, it becomes evident that HTA agencies would benefit from methodological tools and processes that can be flexible enough to serve the individual needs of different HTA agencies or even committees, in a tailormade way; however, at the same time these tools and processes should be characterized by some common value benchmarks in order to be able and draw comparisons between different evaluations by the same agencies (for different decision contexts) and by different agencies (either for the same or different decision contexts). For that purpose, a similar enough but adequately flexible language, for the value analysis and value communication within and between agencies would be vital, which should be characterized by technical characteristics but also being easily adoptable by policy-makers.

Second, the quantitative decision analytic methodological approach developed and tested, holistically represented by the IMPACT-HTA value framework, seems to have a number of benefits relating to the above key requirements. It is characterized by a common but flexible value frame, which can be adapted according to individual HTA agency needs, being able to capture what matters to all relevant stakeholders as part of an engaging socio-technical approach, including experts and decision-makers, and also by how much, given the ability to incorporate and elicit value trade-offs. The empirical applications with the HTA partner agencies for different disease indications demonstrated that by taking into consideration any relevant non-clinical value aspects of new medicines, the results might be different compared to the evaluation based solely on clinical value aspects. The case study work also proved that evaluation results might differ due to differences in the value preferences of different groups of individuals, in that particular case representing members of evaluation committees. However, the existence of such differences should not be represented in a negative way; on the contrary, such variations would be very much expected, and as long as the differences in evaluation results can be identified and explained, any emerging variations in the decision recommendations would also be justifiable, therefore improving the overall transparency of the evaluation and the credibility of the decisions.

Future research could focus on further empirical applications of the IMPACT-HTA value framework, in collaboration with more HTA agencies and for different decision contexts, in order to better understand its benefits and limitations. One point for further research could relate to the development of appropriately defined value benchmarks or value scales, possibly containing separate level definitions according to different therapeutic areas; these could be used to evaluate, score and compare alternative technologies while being possible to more readily adopt the results at implementation level, by linking them with pricing and coverage decisions. Additional case studies could be conducted with HTA agencies currently making use of such value score classifications, as is the case in France and Germany.

Supplementary material

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WP7, Task 3, Supplementary material No. 1

Testing the IMPACT HTA Value Framework in HTA agencies with simulated evaluation committees (steps 1-3)

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Participatory approaches used for developing and testing the IMPACT HTA value framework

Phase 2: Testing at the HTA agency level

Steps for testing the IMPACT HTA value framework in T3

3 main collaborative modelling steps in T3

- HTA agency (aligning HTA agency stakeholders)
 - Adapting the relevant aspects for the HTA agency context to consider in the evaluation of new drugs.
 - Departing from the results from T2, in the interface with T2
 - Classifying the relevant aspects in the categories of importance, for 5 selected disease areas.
 - Discussing the evaluation process and structure.
 - HTA agency committees
 - Testing the use of the framework by simulating real cases
- A. Delphi processes with two HTA agencies, dealt with as case studies
- B. Interviews
- C. Collaborative value modelling with simulated evaluation committees (*case studies*)

Detailing the steps to be performed in Task 3

Steps in T3

Steps in 15

Step 1

Kick off meeting at HTA agency

“Adapting and testing the IMPACT HTA value framework with HTA agencies:
Feedback collection on value aspects, disease-areas,
and relevant stakeholders”

Feedback collection TLV

- Summary of WP7 Task 3 steps
- (i) Feedback collection on completeness of value aspects
- (ii) Feedback collection on relevance of disease-areas
- (iii) Feedback collection on relevant stakeholders

(i) Preliminary list of value aspects for validation:

Is anything missing?

Question for you (TLV):

From the perspective of TLV in Sweden (HTA body), is any relevant value aspect deemed to be missing? At this stage we are not interested to the relevance of each of these aspects, only to whether something is missing.

Answer (of TLV):

Please provide your feedback below

We suggest that you consider including the aspects listed below:

- *Size of patient population*
- *Risk of leakage outside the proposed indication*
- *Risk of drug addiction*

New value
aspects
proposed

TLV also notes that several value aspects overlap and hence some aspects may be double counted.

List of value aspects for TLV after preliminary validation

Aspect name
A - Severity of the disease
B - Unmet need of the disease
C - Medicine's impact on mortality
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life
F - Medicine's adverse events profile
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community
J - Medicine's economic impact
K - Medicine's affordability
L - Medicine's efficiency
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
U - Size of patient population
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
W - Risk of leakage across indications
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity

New value aspects proposed

(ii) Suggested disease area contexts for studying the relevance of the different value aspects: Are these relevant (interesting) for TLV?

1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: 02D),
e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.
2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B),
e.g. spinal muscular atrophy.
3. Forms of heart disease (ICD-10 code: I30-I52),
e.g. congestive heart failure.
4. Inflammatory liver diseases (ICD-10 code: K75),
e.g. non-alcoholic steatohepatitis.
5. Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders (ICD-10 code: F20-F29),
e.g. paranoid schizophrenia.

(ii) Suggested disease area contexts for studying the relevance of the different value aspects: Are these relevant (interesting) for TLV?

Answer (of TLV):

Please provide your feedback below

TLV agrees that the proposed disease area contexts are relevant and interesting. We are especially interested in testing the framework on the following disease areas:

- *Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B), and,*
- *Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders (ICD-10 code: F20-F29)*

TLV is also interested in examples of preventative treatments (e.g., vaccines) and/or non pharmacological treatments (e.g., the MiniMed system)

Agree with the
disease
contexts

(iii) Relevant stakeholders for HTA decision making (evidence assessment and appraisal): Which are relevant for TLV?

Answer (of TLV):

Please provide your feedback below (including contact details for relevant stakeholder representatives to be invited in the web-Delphi)

Please feel free to invite the TLV employees listed below to the web-delphi process:

Niklas Hedberg niklas.hedberg@tlv.se

Douglas Lundin Douglas.Lundin@tlv.se

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Linnea Oldsberg linnea.oldsberg@tlv.se

List with 7
participants

Feedback collection INAMI

- Summary of WP7 Task 3 steps
- (i) Feedback collection on completeness of value aspects
- (ii) Feedback collection on relevance of disease-areas
- (iii) Feedback collection on relevant stakeholders

(i) Preliminary list of value aspects for validation:

Is anything missing?

Question for you (INAMI):

From the perspective of INAMI-RIZIV in Belgium (HTA body), is any relevant value aspect deemed to be missing? At this stage we are not interested to the relevance of each of these aspects, only to whether something is missing.

Answer (of INAMI):

Please provide your feedback below

What is remarkably lacking in the list is the notion of relative therapeutic value of the new medicine: its clinical value versus comparators or versus standard of care, its place in medical practice or pharmacotherapy etc. Please add the notion of 'added therapeutic value' or 'no added therapeutic value' of a new medicine.

New value
aspect
proposed

List of value aspects for TLV after preliminary validation

Aspect name

A - Severity of the disease

B - Unmet need of the disease

C - Medicine's impact on mortality

D - Medicine's impact on morbidity

E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

F - Medicine's adverse events profile

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients

H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

J - Medicine's economic impact

K - Medicine's affordability

L - Medicine's efficiency

M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy

Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality

R - Medicine's time for treatment effect

S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

No new value
aspect
proposed

(ii) Suggested disease area contexts for studying the relevance of the different value aspects: Are these relevant (interesting) for your HTA organisation (e.g. INAMI?)

Answer from you HTA organisation (e.g. INAMI):

Please provide your feedback below

We don't know how these diseases were chosen or by whom.

We would like to see the previous list more mixed, e.g. with

- A disease where a high cost 'one shot' treatment is introduced (e.g. gene transfer): high upfront cost and uncertainty on the long-term results
- An orphan disease where 1 orphan drug is given lifelong. This faces us with an incomplete evidence set at the moment of reimbursement claim. E.g. enzyme replacement therapy in metabolic disease
- A disease where market shifts take place e.g. rheumatoid arthritis: new classes arrives e.g. JAKinhibitors and biosimilars get launched too.

New disease
context
proposed

New disease context for INAMI

1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.
2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.
3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.
4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for non alcoholic steatohepatitis.
5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

(iii) Relevant stakeholders for HTA decision making (evidence assessment and appraisal): Which are relevant for your HTA organisation (e.g. INAMI?)

Answer from you HTA organisation (e.g. INAMI):

Please provide your feedback below (including contact details for relevant stakeholder representatives to be invited in the web-Delphi)

The list of members of the Belgian Reimbursement Commission of Pharmaceuticals is given on a separate list. Hereafter abbreviated as the Commission. The Commission is not only entitled to adopt HTA-reports written by our expert staff but also to vote proposals for reimbursement, prepared by our staff. Therefore the list has two parts: first the voting members and then the non-voting members of the Commission.

We don't have any information as to their availability for Delphi panels. For the moment we know e.g. that academic authorities in Belgium do not allow academics to participate in Commission's activities because of the corona-crisis.

List with 37 participants

Step 2

Delphi in HTA agencies

Detailing the web-Delphi process to be carried out in two HTA agencies (TLV and INAMI)

Steps in T3

Delphi in HTA agencies

Designed to understand:

“The relevance of the following value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in this disease context”

For each value aspect participants were asked to select a level of relevance (Essential, Influential, Complementary or Irrelevant) for each of the five disease context areas

Web-Delphi process design

Example of screen in the Delphi process: Round 1

welphi

Impact HTA - Agencies TLV - R1 | Round 1 | ROUND 1 | Web-Delphi

Consider the following list of potentially relevant aspects for the evaluation of new medicines (on the right). In your opinion, is any aspect missing from the list? If so, please use the fields below to add its name and description. Note that you must repeat the same action for each additional aspect you might want to add. If you believe the list is complete, please click "CONTINUE" without adding anything.

Name

Description

SAVE

	Description	Comment	Edit
1	A - Severity of the disease		
2	B - Unmet need of the disease		
3	C - Medicine's impact on mortality		
4	D - Medicine's impact on morbidity		
5	E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life		
6	F - Medicine's adverse events profile		
7	G - Medicine's tolerability to patients		
8	H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients		
9	I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community		
10	J - Medicine's economic impact		
11	K - Medicine's affordability		
12	L - Medicine's efficiency		
13	M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials		
14	N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care		

← BACK
CONTINUE

Final list of value aspects for TLV

Aspect name
A - Severity of the disease
B - Unmet need of the disease
C - Medicine's impact on mortality
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life
F - Medicine's adverse events profile
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community
J - Medicine's economic impact
K - Medicine's affordability
L - Medicine's efficiency
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
W - Risk of leakage across indications
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity

After the collection feedback and clarification with participants, no new value aspects were added. Aspect "U - Size of patient population" was adapted to "U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)"

Final list of value aspects for INAMI

Aspect name

A - Severity of the disease

B - Unmet need of the disease

C - Medicine's impact on mortality

D - Medicine's impact on morbidity

E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life

F - Medicine's adverse events profile

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients

H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

J - Medicine's economic impact

K - Medicine's affordability

L - Medicine's efficiency

M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy

Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality

R - Medicine's time for treatment effect

S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

V - Medicine's spill-over effects

W - Medicine's mechanism of action

After the collection feedback and clarification with participants, 3 new value aspects were added.

Example of screen in the Delphi process: Round 2

Impact HTA - Agencies TLV | Round 2 | Impact HTA - Agencies TLV | Round 2 | Web-Delphi

DISEASE CONTEXT 1 | DISEASE CONTEXT 2 | DISEASE CONTEXT 3 | DISEASE CONTEXT 4 | DISEASE CONTEXT 5

The relevance of the following value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in this disease context is:

description	ESSENTIAL	INFLUENTIAL	COMPLEMENTARY	IRRELEVANT	DON'T KNOW/DON'T WANT TO ANSWER	comment
1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: O2D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.						
A - Severity of the disease	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
B - Unmet need of the disease	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

← BACK

5 screens for each disease context

Example of screen in the Delphi process: Round 2

The relevance of the following value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in this disease context is:

View previous round comments

description	ESSENTIAL	INFLUENTIAL	COMPLEMENTARY	IRRELEVANT	DON'T KNOW/DON'T WANT TO ANSWER	comment
1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: O2D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.						
A - Severity of the disease	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 67%	<input type="radio"/> 33%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
B - Unmet need of the disease	<input type="radio"/> 22%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 33%	<input type="radio"/> 33%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	<input type="radio"/> 78%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	<input type="radio"/> 56%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 44%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	<input type="radio"/> 56%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 44%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	<input type="radio"/> 22%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 67%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 44%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 56%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 67%	<input type="radio"/> 22%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 44%	<input type="radio"/> 44%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	
J - Medicine's economic impact	<input type="radio"/> 56%	<input type="radio"/> 22%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
K - Medicine's affordability	<input type="radio"/> 22%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 56%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
L - Medicine's efficiency	<input type="radio"/> 78%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 78%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 11%	<input checked="" type="radio"/> 78%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	<input type="radio"/> 0%	

5 screens for each disease context

← BACK

Detailing the relevancy classification

Levels of decreasing (intrinsic) relevance of aspects to assess if the medicine fulfils its designated purpose:

Essential: this aspect must be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it is not possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); it is not possible to reach an evaluation recommendation without explicitly considering performance on this aspect.

Influential: this aspect is highly desirable to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it could still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); the lack of favourable performance on this aspect could influence the decision in a detrimental way, as a desirable benefit may not be captured.

Complementary: this aspect is advantageous to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (without evidence of the medicine's performance on it, it would still be possible to assess if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose); favourable performance on this aspect could act supportively to complement the designated purpose of the medicine, i.e. "nice-to-have".

Irrelevant: this aspect does not necessarily need to be part of the basis of evaluation of the medicine (evidence of the medicine's performance on it, does not influence if the medicine fulfills its designated purpose).

Delphi (TLV and INAMI) timeline and response rate

Dates	Open	Close
Round 1	6th May 2020	25th May 2020
Round 2	18 June 2020	13 July 2020
Round 3	22 July 2020	14 September 2020

HTA agency	No. Invited	R1		R2		R3	
			Drop-out		Drop-out		Drop-out
TLV	11	9	18.2%	8	11.1%	6	25.0%
INAMI	36	17	52.8%	14	17.6%	13	7.1%

Delphi (TLV and INAMI) respondents per stakeholder group

Stakeholder group	TLV			INAMI		
	R1	R2	R3	R1	R2	R3
Health care professionals, e.g. clinicians, pharmacists, etc.				5	3	3
HTA bodies, e.g. HTA committees, evidence assessors, etc.	5	5	4	5	5	5
Industry, e.g. pharmaceutical companies, industry associations, etc.				3	2	1
Payers and policy-makers, e.g. ministry of health, local/central government, etc.	1	1		2	2	2
General population, e.g. tax payers, citizen representatives, etc.				1	1	1
Scientific experts and methodologists, e.g. epidemiologists, health economists, etc.	3	2	2			
Patients and carers, e.g. patient organisations, patient advocates/ carers, etc.						
None of the above				1	1	1
TOTAL	9	8	6	17	14	13

1. How the responses vary per disease context?
2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Some examples....

Results: TLV Round 3

1. How the responses vary per disease context?

Example of a value aspect with a “similar distribution” of responses between disease contexts:

Results: TLV Round 3

1. How the responses vary per disease context?

Example of a value aspect with a “different distribution” of responses between disease contexts:

Results: INAMI Round 3

1. How the responses vary per disease context?

Example of a value aspect with a “similar distribution” of responses between disease contexts:

Results: INAMI Round 3

1. How the responses vary per disease context?

Example of a value aspect with a “different distribution” of responses between disease contexts:

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: 02D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	5	1	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	5	1	0	0
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	0	5	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	0	4	1	1
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	4	2
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	1	4	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	0	2	4
J - Medicine's economic impact	3	2	0	1
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	1	1
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	1	2	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	2	3	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	1	2	1
A - Severity of the disease	3	3	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	3	3	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	3	3	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	0	3	3	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	3	3	0
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	3	0
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	3	3
B - Unmet need of the disease	2	2	2	0
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	2	2	2	0

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B), e.g. spinal muscular atrophy.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	0	5	1	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	0	5	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	1	5	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	5	1
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	1	0	5	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	1	5	0
A - Severity of the disease	4	2	0	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	1	1	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	4	2	0	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	1	4
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	2	4
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	3	1	2	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	2	3	1	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	2	3	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	1	3	2	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	1	1
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	2	1
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	1	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	2	3	1
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	3	3	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	2	2	1	1
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	2	1	2	1

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 3. Forms of heart disease (ICD-10 code: I30-I52), e.g. congestive heart failure..

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	5	1
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	1	5	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	2	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	4	2	0	0
A - Severity of the disease	2	4	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	0	4	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	0	2	4	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	2	4	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	2	4	0
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	1	1	4	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1	1	4	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	0	4	1
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	4	2
J - Medicine's economic impact	3	2	1	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	2	3	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	1	0	3	1
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	1	2	3	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	3	3	0	0
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	0	3	3
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	2	2	2

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 4. Inflammatory liver diseases (ICD-10 code: K75), e.g. non-alcoholic steatohepatitis.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	0	6	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	5	1
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	2	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	4	1	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	1	1	4	0
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	4	2
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	2	1	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	3	2	1	0
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	3	1	2	0
A - Severity of the disease	2	3	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	1	3	2	0
K - Medicine's affordability	1	3	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	2	3	1	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	0	2
W - Risk of leakage across indications	1	3	2	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	2	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	3	2
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	1	3	0
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	2	1	3	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	3	3	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	3	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	2	2	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	2	2	2

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 5. Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders (ICD-10 code: F20-F29), e.g. paranoid schizophrenia.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	1	5	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	1	0	1
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	4	2	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	4	2	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	0	4	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	0	4	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	2	4	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	1	3	2	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	2	3	1	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	1	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	2	1	3	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	1	2	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	3	2
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1	2	3	0
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	2	3	1
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	2	1	3	0
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	1	2	3	0
A - Severity of the disease	3	3	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	3	0
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	2	2	2
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	2	1	2	1

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	0	0	10	3
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	9	4	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	9	4	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	8	4	1	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	8	4	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	4	8	1
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1	2	8	2
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	7	6	0	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	7	4	1	1
K - Medicine's affordability	7	5	0	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	7	5	1	0
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	2	3	7	1
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	0	4	7	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	6	4	1	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	4	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	2	3	6	2
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	2	1	6	3
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	4	6	3
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	5	4	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	5	5	3	0

Results: INAMI Round 3

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	9	4	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	8	2	2	1
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	8	5	0	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	5	8	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	3	8	2
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	7	6	0	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	7	4	2	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	6	7	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	7	5
J - Medicine's economic impact	6	5	1	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	1	6	5	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	4	6	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	3	6	3
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	2	6	4
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	2	5	2
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	5	3	4	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	6	6	1	0
4 Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	5	3	5	0

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	13	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	10	2	0	1
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	9	4	0	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	8	3	1	1
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	1	2	8	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	4	8	1
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	0	1	8	3
A - Severity of the disease	7	4	1	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	7	6	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	7	4	1	1
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	6	7	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	3	7	3
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	2	7	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	6	5	1	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	6	5	2	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	3	6	4	0
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	3	6	3	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	5	6	2	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	2	4	6	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	4	4	5	0
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	3	4	3	2
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	6	1	0

Results: INAMI Round 3

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for nonalcoholic steatohepatitis.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	13	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	11	1	0	1
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1
A - Severity of the disease	9	3	0	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	9	2	1	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	8	5	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	8	5	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	8	3	0	2
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	8	5	0	0
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	1	4	8	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	7	5	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	7	4	2	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1	7	5	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	2	7	3
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	4	6	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	3	3	6	1
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	5	2	6	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	1	4	6	1
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	5	4	1	3
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	3	4	5	1
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1	3	5	3
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	5	5	1

Results: INAMI Round 3

2. What are the essential, influential, complementary and irrelevant aspects in each disease context?

Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
J - Medicine's economic impact	11	0	1	1
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	10	2	0	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	10	2	1	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	9	3	0	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	9	3	0	1
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	9	3	0	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	9	2	0	2
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	3	9	1	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	8	1	2	2
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	3	8	2
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	1	7	2
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	4	2	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	6	4	2	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	3	6	3	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	3	2	2	6
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	3	1	6
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	0	4	3	6
A - Severity of the disease	5	4	3	1
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	4	5	1	3
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	3	5	4	1
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	4	5	3
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	2	5	5	1

Step 3

Interviews with agency members

Agency consultation for bridging the web-Delphi results
with case study applications

Task 3 main steps

Interviews with agency members - TLV

Participants:

- Douglas Lundin
- Niklas Hedberg

Interviewers:

- Aris Angelis
- Panos Kanavos
- Klára Dimitrovová

Dates:

- 18 November 2020 (12h30-13h30)
- 20 November 2020 (14h00-15h00)

Interviews with agency members - TLV

Objectives:

Introduction

- Task 3 background
- Web-Delphi summary

Discussion

- Validation of web-Delphi results
- Selection of case study topics
- Feedback on web-Delphi experience

Interviews with agency members - TLV

Objectives:

Introduction

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- **Validation of web-Delphi results**
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- Feedback collection on web-Delphi experience

Interviews with agency members - TLV

- **Validation of web-Delphi results:**

“Do you agree that the relevance of each value aspect is the following?”

Participants were asked to validate the results obtained in the Web-Delphi, having the possibility to:

- Change the relevance of any value aspects that they did not agree:
 - Upgrades are marked in green
 - Downgrades are marked in yellow
- Acceptation of Web-Delphi results, with selection of final classification: marked in dark grey

Results from the Web-Delphi: TLV Round 3

Disease Context 1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: 02D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	5	1	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	5	1	0	0
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	0	5	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	0	4	1	1
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	4	2
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	1	4	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	0	2	4
J - Medicine's economic impact	3	2	0	1
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	1	1
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	1	2	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	2	3	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	1	2	1
A - Severity of the disease	3	3	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	3	3	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	3	3	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	0	3	3	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	3	3	0
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	3	0
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	3	3
B - Unmet need of the disease	2	2	2	0
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	2	2	2	0

Disease Context 1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: 02D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

L - Medicine's efficiency

“overlapping with mortality, very relevant because of mortality component”

S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

“overlapping with mortality?”

D - Medicine's impact on morbidity:

“mortality more important, so should be influential”

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients:

“given the severity of the disease, prepared to take more risk”

U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)

“if very rare then influential; if just rare then complementary; more because of political reasons and societal pressure”

Results from the Web-Delphi: TLV Round 3

Disease Context 2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B), e.g. spinal muscular atrophy.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	0	5	1	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	0	5	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	1	5	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	5	1
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	1	0	5	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	1	5	0
A - Severity of the disease	4	2	0	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	1	1	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	4	2	0	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	1	4
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	2	4
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	3	1	2	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	2	3	1	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	2	3	1	0
K - Medicine's affordability	1	3	2	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	1	1
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	2	1
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	1	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	2	3	1
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	3	3	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	2	2	1	1
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	2	1	2	1

Disease Context 2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B), e.g. spinal muscular atrophy.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials.

“At least influential; reflects willingness to accept more risk; we may accept a lower quality because we know it is an orphan drug.”

U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)

“e.g. Spinraza”

W - Risk of leakage across indications

“Performance based agreements as potential protections tools”

P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy

“e.g. Spinraza”

D - Medicine's impact on morbidity, E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life, Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality, V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication

“D,E,Q,V of same relevance”

Results from the Web-Delphi: TLV Round 3

Disease Context 3. Forms of heart disease (ICD-10 code: I30-I52), e.g. congestive heart failure.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	5	1
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	1	5	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	2	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	4	2	0	0
A - Severity of the disease	2	4	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	0	4	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	0	2	4	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	2	4	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	2	4	0
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	1	1	4	0
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1	1	4	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	0	4	1
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	4	2
J - Medicine's economic impact	3	2	1	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	2	3	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	1	0	3	1
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	1	2	3	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	3	3	0	0
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	0	3	3
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	2	2	2

Disease Context 3. Forms of heart disease (ICD-10 code: I30-I52), e.g. congestive heart failure.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

A - Severity of the disease

“Not essential because less severe disease”

K - Medicine's affordability

“Veto: not that relevant for TLV”

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients

“If long-term chronic could also be influential because it could impact adherence”

R - Medicine's time for treatment effect

“i.e. secondary prevention purpose”

E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life

“Same as in previous contexts”

Results from the Web-Delphi: TLV Round 3

Disease Context 4. Inflammatory liver diseases (ICD-10 code: K75), e.g. non-alcoholic steatohepatitis.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	0	6	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	0	5	1
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	2	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	4	1	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	1	1	4	0
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	0	4	2
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	2	1	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	3	2	1	0
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	3	1	2	0
A - Severity of the disease	2	3	1	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	1	3	2	0
K - Medicine's affordability	1	3	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	2	3	1	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	0	2
W - Risk of leakage across indications	1	3	2	0
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	1	2	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	3	2
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	1	3	0
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	2	1	3	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	3	3	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	0	3	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	2	2	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	2	2	2

Disease Context 4. Inflammatory liver diseases (ICD-10 code: K75), e.g. non-alcoholic steatohepatitis.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)

“Veto: probably not rare so not that relevant”

K - Medicine's affordability

“As previously”

R - Medicine's time for treatment effect

“Not so acute disease”

W - Risk of leakage across indications

“Not really a value aspect but considered in the decision”

I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

“e.g. HPV”

Results from the Web-Delphi: TLV Round 3

Disease Context 5. Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders (ICD-10 code: F20-F29), e.g. paranoid schizophrenia.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	0	1	5	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	4	1	0	1
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	4	2	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	4	2	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	0	4	2	0
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	1	4	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	1	4	1	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	0	4	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	0	2	4	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	1	3	2	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	2	3	1	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	3	1	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	2	1	3	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	1	2	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	3	2
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1	2	3	0
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	2	3	1
U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)	2	1	3	0
V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication	1	2	3	0
A - Severity of the disease	3	3	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	3	3	0	0
W - Risk of leakage across indications	0	3	3	0
X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity	0	2	2	2
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	2	1	2	1

Disease Context 5. Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders (ICD-10 code: F20-F29), e.g. paranoid schizophrenia.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

C - Medicine's impact on mortality

“Not that relevant for schizophrenia”

K - Medicine's affordability

“As before”

T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

“More important for the disease”

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients

“More important for the disease”

Interviews with agency members - TLV

Objectives:

Introduction

- Task 3 background
- Web-Delphi summary

Discussion

- Validation of web-Delphi results
- **Selection of case study topics**
- Feedback collection on web-Delphi experience

To be
validated
by TLV

Disease Context 1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: 02D)

Indication:

Advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), either i) with epidermal growth factor EGFR mutation (+) or ii) not (-)

Interventions:

(EGFR-) a) PD-1 immunotherapies vs platinum doublet (1st line), or b) PD-1 immunotherapies vs single-agent chemotherapy (2nd line)

(EGFR+) a) TKIs vs platinum doublet (1st line), or b) PD-1 immunotherapies vs platinum doublet (2nd/3rd lines)

Disease Context 2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B)

Indication:

spinal muscular atrophy

Interventions:

onasemnogene abeparvovec (Zolgensma) vs nusinersen (Spinraza) vs Best Supportive Care

Interviews with agency members - TLV

Objectives:

Introduction

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- Validation of web-Delphi results
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Interviews with agency members - TLV

- **Feedback collection on web-Delphi experience:**

Participants were asked to provide any feedback in terms of:

- Medicines' value aspects (e.g. new aspects)
- Diseases' contextual considerations (e.g. more structured)
- Delphi consensus approach (e.g. more deliberative)
- Differences/commonalities in terms of current thinking

Summary of feedback collected:

General comments:

- “Many aspects are not mutually exclusive”; “challenge of not to think about double counting of the value aspects” (regarding to this point, the participants were instructed to think about each value aspect as “stand-alone”)
- “There is a difference between value perceptions and affordability concerns, e.g. ease of use is valuable for patients, but payers are not willing to pay”
- “The relevancy of each value aspect may differ according to the perspective (HTA, payer, patient...)”

Summary of feedback collected:

Feedback about Web-Delphi:

- “Well designed, very clear, useful.”
- “Easy and convenient to answer.”
- “Not very time consuming.”
- “Disadvantage: not possible to discuss with other people the interpretation of aspects.”

Final classification of Web-Delphi results:

TYPE OF INFO TO BE GIVEN TO COMMITTEES

TLV

1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: O2D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.

Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A - Severity of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life J - Medicine's economic impact L - Medicine's efficiency
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> B - Unmet need of the disease D - Medicine's impact on morbidity K - Medicine's affordability M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials R - Medicine's time for treatment effect S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s) W - Risk of leakage across indications
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F - Medicine's adverse events profile G - Medicine's tolerability to patients H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity) V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
Irrelevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity

2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B), e.g. spinal muscular atrophy.

Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">A - Severity of the diseaseC - Medicine's impact on mortalityD - Medicine's impact on morbidityE - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of lifeL - Medicine's efficiencyQ - Medicines' impact on patient functionalityU - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">B - Unmet need of the diseaseJ - Medicine's economic impactK - Medicine's affordabilityM - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trialsR - Medicine's time for treatment effectS - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)W - Risk of leakage across indications
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none">F - Medicine's adverse events profileG - Medicine's tolerability to patientsH - Medicine's ease and convenience for patientsN - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of careO - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issuesP - Medicine's value as a bridge therapyT - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
Irrelevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none">I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the communityX - Risk of drug addiction and its severity

3. Forms of heart disease (ICD-10 code: I30-I52), e.g. congestive heart failure.

Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> C - Medicine's impact on mortality D - Medicine's impact on morbidity E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life J - Medicine's economic impact L - Medicine's efficiency
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A - Severity of the disease M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> B - Unmet need of the disease F - Medicine's adverse events profile G - Medicine's tolerability to patients H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients K - Medicine's affordability N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality R - Medicine's time for treatment effect T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity) V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication W - Risk of leakage across indications X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity
Irrelevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

4. Inflammatory liver diseases (ICD-10 code: K75), e.g. non-alcoholic steatohepatitis.

Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">C - Medicine's impact on mortalityD - Medicine's impact on morbidityE - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of lifeJ - Medicine's economic impactL - Medicine's efficiency
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">A - Severity of the diseaseB - Unmet need of the diseaseG - Medicine's tolerability to patientsK - Medicine's affordabilityM - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trialsQ - Medicines' impact on patient functionalityS - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)W - Risk of leakage across indications
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none">F - Medicine's adverse events profileH - Medicine's ease and convenience for patientsI - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the communityN - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of careO - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issuesP - Medicine's value as a bridge therapyR - Medicine's time for treatment effectT - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)V - Risk of leakage within licensed indicationX - Risk of drug addiction and its severity
Irrelevant	-

5. Schizophrenia, schizotypal and delusional disorders (ICD-10 code: F20-F29), e.g. paranoid schizophrenia.

Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A - Severity of the disease D - Medicine's impact on morbidity E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life L - Medicine's efficiency
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> B - Unmet need of the disease C - Medicine's impact on mortality G - Medicine's tolerability to patients H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients J - Medicine's economic impact M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality R - Medicine's time for treatment effect S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s) T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> F - Medicine's adverse events profile I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community K - Medicine's affordability N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity) V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication W - Risk of leakage across indications X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity
Irrelevant	-

Interviews with agency members - INAMI

Participants:

- Marc Van de Castele
- Francis Arickx

Interviewers:

- Aris Angelis
- Panos Kanavos
- Klára Dimitrovová

Dates:

- 19 November 2020 (14h00-15h00)
- 23 November 2020 (12h00-13h00)

Interviews with agency members - INAMI

Objectives:

Introduction

- Task 3 background
- Web-Delphi summary

Discussion

- Validation of web-Delphi results
- Selection of case study topics
- Feedback on web-Delphi experience

Interviews with agency members - INAMI

Objectives:

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Interviews with agency members - INAMI

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“Do you agree that the relevance of each value aspect is the following?”

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- Change the relevance of any value aspects that they did not agree:
 - Upgrades are marked in green
 - Downgrades are marked in yellow
- Acceptation of Web-Delphi results, with selection of final classification: marked in dark grey

Results from the Web-Delphi: INAMI Round 3

Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	0	0	10	3
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	9	4	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	9	4	0	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	8	4	1	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	8	4	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	0	4	8	1
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	1	2	8	2
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	7	6	0	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	7	4	1	1
K - Medicine's affordability	7	5	0	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	7	5	1	0
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	2	3	7	1
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	0	4	7	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	6	4	1	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	4	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	2	3	6	2
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	2	1	6	3
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	4	6	3
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	5	4	0
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	5	5	3	0

Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients

“Personally, lower grade but agree with results”

O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues

“Typical would be complementary, seems to be shifting towards higher grade”

I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

“Typical would be complementary, seems to be shifting towards higher grade”

T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

“Influential, otherwise same level with mortality”

Results from the Web-Delphi: INAMI Round 3

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	12	1	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	0	9	4	0
B - Unmet need of the disease	8	2	2	1
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	8	5	0	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	0	5	8	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	3	8	2
A - Severity of the disease	7	3	2	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	7	6	0	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	7	4	2	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	6	7	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	1	7	5
J - Medicine's economic impact	6	5	1	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	6	5	1	1
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	1	6	5	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	4	6	3	0
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	3	6	3
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	2	6	4
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	2	5	2
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	5	3	4	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	6	6	1	0
8 Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	5	3	5	0

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

K - Medicine's affordability

“Irrelevant: person might be right as the relevance results from political pressure!”

H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

“Split makes sense, seems to be shifting towards higher grade”

A - Severity of the disease

“Complete range, bizarre”

F - Medicine's adverse events profile

“Personally influential”

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients

“Would have expected the same with medicine's adverse events (F)”

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

L - Medicine's efficiency

“Orphan disease, bizarre”

N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

“One grade up compared to previous context”

M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

“ Less important than mortality etc”

Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality

“In between”

Results from the Web-Delphi: INAMI Round 3

Disease Context 3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	13	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0
K - Medicine's affordability	10	2	0	1
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	9	4	0	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	8	3	1	1
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	1	2	8	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	4	8	1
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	0	1	8	3
A - Severity of the disease	7	4	1	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	7	6	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	7	4	1	1
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	6	7	0	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	0	3	7	3
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	2	7	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	6	5	1	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	6	5	2	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	3	6	4	0
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	3	6	3	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	5	6	2	0
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	2	4	6	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	4	4	5	0
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	3	4	3	2
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	6	1	0

Disease Context 3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

W - Medicine's mechanism of action

“Personally irrelevant”

F - Medicine's adverse events profile

“Yes, if you have alternatives!”

M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

“Would have expected influential”

Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality

“Upgrade, would expect influential, more like the mean “

S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

“Less important than mortality”

Results from the Web-Delphi: INAMI Round 3

Disease Context 4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for nonalcoholic steatohepatitis.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	13	0	0	0
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	12	1	0	0
J - Medicine's economic impact	11	1	0	1
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1
A - Severity of the disease	9	3	0	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	9	2	1	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	8	5	0	0
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	8	5	0	0
L - Medicine's efficiency	8	3	0	2
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	8	5	0	0
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	1	4	8	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	7	5	1	0
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	7	4	2	0
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	1	7	5	0
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	2	7	3
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	4	6	3	0
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	3	3	6	1
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	5	2	6	0
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	1	4	6	1
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	5	4	1	3
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	3	4	5	1
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	1	3	5	3
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	5	5	1

Disease Context 4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for nonalcoholic steatohepatitis.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

J - Medicine's economic impact

“Would have expected influential, but fine”

K - Medicine's affordability

“Non-validated endpoints, not clear results, need time”

A - Severity of the disease

“Would have expected influential but fine”

B - Unmet need of the disease

“Makes sense, included in the title!”

F - Medicine's adverse events profile

“Observation comment: in generally mortality essential by unanimous, AE essential but less consensus”

M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials

“Because of endpoints use, unknown clinical outcomes”

Disease Context 4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for nonalcoholic steatohepatitis.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality

“Not so important for NASH”

S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

“Life-long treatment”

H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients

“Life-long treatment”

I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community

“Less relevant for the disease”

U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

“Although not rare, still justified because title says high-prevalence (with unmet need)”

Results from the Web-Delphi: INAMI Round 3

Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

Value Aspect	Essential	Influential	Complementary	Irrelevant
J - Medicine's economic impact	11	0	1	1
K - Medicine's affordability	11	1	0	1
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	10	2	0	1
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	10	2	1	0
E - Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	9	3	0	1
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	9	3	0	1
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	9	3	0	1
L - Medicine's efficiency	9	2	0	2
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	3	9	1	0
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	8	1	2	2
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	0	3	8	2
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	2	1	7	2
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	6	4	2	1
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	6	4	2	1
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	3	6	3	1
B - Unmet need of the disease	3	2	2	6
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	0	3	1	6
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	0	4	3	6
A - Severity of the disease	5	4	3	1
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	4	5	1	3
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	3	5	4	1
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	1	4	5	3
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	2	5	5	1

Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

J - Medicine's economic impact

“Because many options available, both on and off patent!”

K - Medicine's affordability

“Because many options available, both on and off patent!”

E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life

“Chronic disease with many options”

F - Medicine's adverse events profile

“Chronic disease with many options”

G - Medicine's tolerability to patients

“Chronic disease with many options”

C - Medicine's impact on mortality

“Strange the 2 irrelevant”

Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

Comments regarding to value aspects:

S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)

“Personally influential but fine”

T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)

“Would have expected influential, but makes sense because of many options”

B - Unmet need of the disease

“Many treatments available!”

P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy

“Many treatments available!”

U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)

“Many treatments available!”

N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care

“Because many options”

Interviews with agency members - INAMI

Objectives:

Introduction

- Task 3 background
- Web-Delphi summary

Discussion

- Validation of web-Delphi results
- **Selection of case study topics**
- Feedback collection on web-Delphi experience

Selection of case study topics – INAMI disease contexts

To be
validated
by INAMI

Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available

Indication:

Advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), either i) with epidermal growth factor EGFR mutation (+) or ii) not (-)

Interventions:

(EGFR-) a) PD-1 immunotherapies vs platinum doublet (1st line), or b) PD-1 immunotherapies vs single-agent chemotherapy (2nd line)

(EGFR+) a) TKIs vs platinum doublet (1st line), or b) PD-1 immunotherapies vs platinum doublet (2nd/3rd lines)

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits

Indication:

spinal muscular atrophy

Interventions:

onasemnogene abeparvovec (Zolgensma) vs nusinersen (Spinraza) vs Best Supportive Care

Interviews with agency members - INAMI

Objectives:

Introduction

- Task 3 background
- Web-Delphi summary

Discussion

- Validation of web-Delphi results
- Selection of case study topics
- **Feedback collection on web-Delphi experience**

Interviews with agency members - TLV

- **Feedback collection on web-Delphi experience:**

Participants were asked to provide any feedback in terms of:

- Medicines' value aspects (e.g. new aspects)
- Diseases' contextual considerations (e.g. more structured)
- Delphi consensus approach (e.g. more deliberative)
- Differences/commonalities in terms of current thinking

Summary of feedback collected:

General comments:

- “Less reluctant to say irrelevant in the last context, if there is uncertainty more reluctant to say so!”
- “Maybe too many aspect, more practical to have fewer”
- “Surprised from time to time with answers but then understood the rationale, happy with the way it works”
- “If had done this publicly/anonymously would probably have different results!”
- “People were less reluctant, less political, because of secret vote”

Summary of feedback collected:

General comments:

- “Some aspects votes by majority, interested in how to compare consensus degree more scientifically”
- “In real Belgian settings, consensus voting needs 2/3 of majority, if not then vote something else or come back later”
- “In general mortality, morbidity, HRQOL, economic, affordability, efficiency are the most important”
- “From time-to-time other value aspects pop up depending on the context, eg duration of treatment and time to effect when there are many options”
- “In terms of exercise usefulness, Mark will share results internally”

Summary of feedback collected:

Feedback about Web-Delphi:

- “In terms of web-Delphi, the anonymous feature could be potentially useful for Belgium and INAMI, e.g. industry present in the room, could be less politically correct and more radical”

Final classification of Web-Delphi results:

**TYPE OF INFO TO BE GIVEN TO COMMITTEES
INAMI**

Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.

Essential	<p>A - Severity of the disease</p> <p>B - Unmet need of the disease</p> <p>C - Medicine's impact on mortality</p> <p>D - Medicine's impact on morbidity</p> <p>E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life</p> <p>F - Medicine's adverse events profile</p> <p>G - Medicine's tolerability to patients</p> <p>J - Medicine's economic impact</p> <p>K - Medicine's affordability</p> <p>L - Medicine's efficiency</p> <p>M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials</p> <p>S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p>
Influential	<p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)</p>
Complementary	<p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	-

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.

Essential	<p>A - Severity of the disease</p> <p>B - Unmet need of the disease</p> <p>C - Medicine's impact on mortality</p> <p>D - Medicine's impact on morbidity</p> <p>E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life</p> <p>F - Medicine's adverse events profile</p> <p>J - Medicine's economic impact</p> <p>K - Medicine's affordability</p> <p>L - Medicine's efficiency</p> <p>S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p>
Influential	<p>G - Medicine's tolerability to patients</p> <p>M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)</p>
Complementary	<p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	-

Disease Context 3. Orphan disease with a number of symptomatic treatments that need to be taken over lifetime, as monotherapy or in combination, e.g. new therapeutic agents acting at the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator (CFTR) channel.

Essential	<p>A - Severity of the disease</p> <p>B - Unmet need of the disease</p> <p>C - Medicine's impact on mortality</p> <p>D - Medicine's impact on morbidity</p> <p>E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life</p> <p>F - Medicine's adverse events profile</p> <p>J - Medicine's economic impact</p> <p>K - Medicine's affordability</p> <p>L - Medicine's efficiency</p> <p>M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials</p>
Influential	<p>G - Medicine's tolerability to patients</p> <p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p> <p>T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p>
Complementary	<p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	-

Disease Context 4. High prevalence emerging disease with high unmet need for which no available treatments exist, possibly combined with incomplete clinical guidelines/ pathways and non-validated clinical endpoints, e.g. treatments under development for non alcoholic steatohepatitis.

Essential	<p>A - Severity of the disease</p> <p>B - Unmet need of the disease</p> <p>C - Medicine's impact on mortality</p> <p>D - Medicine's impact on morbidity</p> <p>E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life</p> <p>F - Medicine's adverse events profile</p> <p>G - Medicine's tolerability to patients</p> <p>J - Medicine's economic impact</p> <p>K - Medicine's affordability</p> <p>L - Medicine's efficiency</p> <p>M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials</p> <p>S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p>
Influential	<p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)</p>
Complementary	<p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	-

Disease Context 5. High prevalence chronic disease with different therapeutic classes available, both on patent and off patent, e.g. Jak inhibitors and TNF-alpha biosimilars for rheumatoid arthritis.

Essential	<p>A - Severity of the disease</p> <p>C - Medicine's impact on mortality</p> <p>D - Medicine's impact on morbidity</p> <p>E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life</p> <p>F - Medicine's adverse events profile</p> <p>G - Medicine's tolerability to patients</p> <p>J - Medicine's economic impact</p> <p>K - Medicine's affordability</p> <p>L - Medicine's efficiency</p> <p>M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials</p> <p>S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p> <p>T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)</p>
Influential	<p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p>
Complementary	<p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	<p>B - Unmet need of the disease</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p>

Discussing the steps forward in Task 3: preparing decision conferences

All TLV aspects

Health Outcomes Component

- C - Medicine's impact on mortality
- D - Medicine's impact on morbidity
- E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life
- F - Medicine's adverse events profile
- G - Medicine's tolerability to patients
- P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy
- Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality
- R - Medicine's time for treatment effect
- S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)
- T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
- X - Risk of drug addiction and its severity

Other Components

- A - Severity of the disease
- B - Unmet need of the disease
- H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients
- I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community
- J - Medicine's economic impact
- K - Medicine's affordability
- L - Medicine's efficiency
- M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials
- N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care
- O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues
- U - Size of patient population
- V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
- W - Risk of leakage across indications

Example of classification
of TLV aspects into health
outcomes and other
components
(for validation)

Example of possible model structure, for agencies used to
CUA – model structures depend on the agency/committee
views

IMPACT-HTA VALUE TREE TLV

IMPACT-HTA VALUE TREE TLV

MODEL 2

IMPACT-HTA VALUE TREE TLV

NOTE THAT THE ASPECTS
VARY ACROSS DISEASE
INDICATIONS (e.g. some were
found irrelevant)

WP7, Task 3, Supplementary material No. 2

Testing the IMPACT HTA Value Framework in HTA agencies with simulated evaluation committees (step 4)

Mónica Oliveira, Carlos Bana e Costa, Ana
Vieira, Klára Dimitrovová (IST, U Lisboa)
Panos Kanavos, Aris Angelis (LSE)

Step 4 in Task 3

Delphi-MACBETH collaborative value modelling web-framework for treatments' evaluation: Two-step interactive process

Non-face-to-face phase Web-questionnaire

A Web-questionnaire with the agency panel members for each of two therapeutic indications to:

- Elicit individual qualitative (non-numerical) judgements about differences in value between treatments.
- Align and acquire knowledge to motivate face-to-face discussion.

Technical support: Welphi platform

Objective:

- Collect individual value judgments about the treatments on key value aspects, based on clinical evidence.

Participants' task:

- Each participant provides their judgment by choosing the qualitative judgements about the difference in value between treatments, based on MACBETH scale.

Output:

- Group majority judgements about the difference in value between treatments to reach value aspects scores and weights for developing a prototype value model.

Face-to-face phase Virtual decision conference

A two-day Virtual decision conference with the agency panel to structure and build the multicriteria additive value model by defining weights for the evaluation aspects and value scores for the treatments.

Technical support: Welphi and Wisedon platforms.

Objective:

- Develop a shared multicriteria value model and discuss and validate its outputs.

Participants' task:

- Group discussion and alignment on prototype value model qualitative judgements about the difference in value between treatments, based on MACBETH scale.

Output:

- Multicriteria value model for evaluating the added-value of treatments.

Socio-technical design: alternative strategies for setting value aspects' (partial) scores

Socio-technical design: alternative strategies for weighting value aspects

Facilitation Team

Facilitator:

- João Bana e Costa

LSE Support Team:

- Aris Angelis
- Panos Kanavos

IST Support Team:

- Teresa Rodrigues
- Liliana Freitas
- Mónica Oliveira
- Carlos Bana e Costa
- Marta Belchior

Simulated committees: participants

INAMI participants for NSCLC case study:

- Barbara Claus
- Caroline Lebbe
- Diane Kleinermans
- Joël Daems
- Lisa Vervueren
- Maëlle Anciaux
- Marc Van De Castele
- Piet Vancraeynest
- Pol Specenier
- Simon Roels

INAMI participants for SMA case study:

- Caroline Lebbe
- Lisa Vervueren
- Maëlle Anciaux
- Marc Van De Castele
- Piet Vancraeynest
- Simon Roels
- Anne Hendrickx
- Filip Clinck

Data collection for NSCLC treatments

To be revised by LSE

				Nivolumab CheckMate 057	Docetaxel CheckMate 057	Nivolumab CheckMate 017	Docetaxel CheckMate 017	Pembrolizumab Keynote-010	Docetaxel Keynote-010	Atezolizumab OAK	Docetaxel OAK
Clusters	Criteria	Attribute name	Attribute metric	Compound A	Compound D	Compound A	Compound D	Compound B	Compound D	Compound C	Compound D
Medicine's Efficiency	Cost	Medicine cost	Cost per mg, as reported by the Institute for Clinical and Economic Review (ICER)	\$24,70	Not available	\$24,70	Not available	\$43,81	Not available	\$7,18	Not available
Medicine's Efficiency	Cost	Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER)	ICER (versus docetaxel) as reported by ICER, \$/QALY	\$415,950 compared to Docetaxel		\$415,950 compared to Docetaxel		\$236,492 compared to docetaxel		\$219,179 compared to Docetaxel	
Medicine's Efficiency	Cost	Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio (ICER)	ICER as reported by NICE, £/QALY	Compared with docetaxel: £49,160 per QALY gained in the full non-squamous NSCLC population, irrespective of programmed death-ligand 1 (PD-L1).		Compared with docetaxel: £50,014 per QALY compared with docetaxel for the full squamous NSCLC population, irrespective of programmed death-		Compared with docetaxel: Ranges between £61,954 per QALY gained (with a 3-year treatment effect) to £44,490 per QALY gained (with a lifetime treatment effect).		Compared with pembrolizumab: the ICER was within the range.	Not available
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	QALYs as estimated by ICER TO BE REPLACED	0,83	0,57	0,83	0,57	1,44	0,57	1,08	0,57
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Average change from baseline for HRQoL, EORTC QLQ-C30, least squares (LS) mean difference	NR	NR	NR	NR	2,7	NR	3,08	NR
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Average change from baseline for HRQoL, EORTC QLQ-C30, least squares (LS) mean difference, range	NR	NR	NR	NR	(-1.05) - 6.36	NR	NR	NR
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on health related quality of life	Average change from baseline for HRQoL, EORTC QLQ-C30, least squares (LS) mean difference, P-value	NR	NR	NR	NR	p=0.1602	NR	p=0.1257	NR
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on mortality	Medicine's impact on health related quality of life: LYs gained as estimated by ICER	1,47	1,04	1,47	1,04	2,59	1,04	2,02	1,04

Data collection for SMA treatments

To be revised by LSE

				Zolgensma / STR1VE US	Zolgensma / STR1VE EU	Zolgensma / STR1VE EU/US combined data	Spinraza / ENDEAR	Best Supportive Care/ ENDEAR	Evrysdi / FIREFISH Part 2
Clusters	Criteria	Value aspect name	Value aspect metric	Compound A		Compound B	Compound C	Compound D	
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on mortality	Event-free survival, % of patients	91%	94%	93%	61%	32%	85%
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on morbidity	Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %	64%	19%	37%	10%	0%	29%
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's impact on morbidity	Patients able to feed orally and did not require nutritional support, %	86%	67%	75%	NR	NR	74%
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcomes value	Medicine's adverse events profile	% of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)	41%	55%	49%	60%	56%	51%
Medicine's Efficiency	Medicine's Outcome value	Medicine's tolerability to patients	% of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation	9%	NR	9%	16%	39%	0%
Medicine's Efficiency	Cost	Total cost of treatment with the drug	Total costs of the drug (include drug treatment costs and non-treatment healthcare costs) as estimated by the Institute for Clinical and Economic Review (ICER)	\$3.657.000			\$3.884.000	\$789,00	Not available
Innovation Level	Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Delivery system and posology	Combination of the delivery system and the posology (i.e. dosing)	One-time IV infusion (reduced complexity)			intravenous, an induction period (4 loading doses) is followed by life-	N/A	Administered orally once daily
Innovation Level	Mechanism of action	Mechanism of action	The technology's mechanism of action	Recombinant AAV9-based gene therapy designed to deliver a copy of the gene encoding the human SMN protein.			oligonucleotide (ASO) designed to treat SMA caused by mutations in	N/A	neuron 2 (SMN2) splicing modifier designed to treat patients with SMA
Other - care organization	adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	Need for specialised hospital setting	Need for specialised hospital setting	Provided at high specialist centres. Before administration of onasemnogene abeparvovec, baseline laboratory testing is required, including: AAV9 antibody testing using an appropriately validated assay, liver function: alanine			others primarily at academic medical center. At baseline and prior to each	N/A	Administered at-home

Setting case studies

Case study with INAMI and TLV agencies for both second line non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) and for spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.

For each of the NSCLC and SMA case studies: two-step interactive process with committee members

Non-face-to-face phase

A Web-questionnaire with INAMI and TLV agency panel members for each therapeutic indications.

Objective:

- to collect individual qualitative (non-numerical) judgements about differences in value between treatments
- to align and acquire knowledge to motivate face-to-face discussion.

Participants' task:

- Each participant provides their judgment by choosing the qualitative judgements about the difference in value between each of the three treatments and the comparator, based on MACBETH scale.

Output:

- Group majority judgements about the difference in value between each of the three treatments and the comparator for the value aspects.

Technical support: Welphi platform

Face-to-face phase

A one-day Virtual decision conference with with INAMI and TLV agency panel members for each therapeutic indications.

Objective:

- to develop a shared multicriteria model based on group discussion of the prototype to calculate a value score for each treatment
- to discuss and validate the model outputs

Participants' task:

- Group discussion and alignment on qualitative judgements about the difference in value between each of the three treatments and the comparator, based on MACBETH scale.

Output:

- Multicriteria value model for evaluating the added-value of of the three treatments.

Technical support: Wisedon platform

Overview of NSCLC case study with INAMI and TLV agencies

- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects involved:
 - Web-questionnaire in which participants expressed individual qualitative value judgments about three immunotherapy treatments (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), based on clinical evidence (and taking into account the aspects' relevance).
 - Preparation of prototype model derived from the results of the web-questionnaire applying decision majority rules.
 - Virtual decision conference to develop a shared model based on group discussion of the prototype to calculate a value score for each treatment.

Overview of SMA case study with INAMI and TLV agencies

- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects involved:
 - Web-questionnaire in which participants expressed individual qualitative value judgments judgments three SMA treatments (Zolgensma, Spinraza and Evrysdi) relatively to a Best Supportive Care, based on clinical evidence (and taking into account the aspects' relevance).
 - Preparation of prototype model derived from the results of the web-questionnaire applying decision majority rules.
 - Virtual decision conference to develop a shared model based on group discussion of the prototype to calculate a value score for each treatment.
- Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects. (Model 2)
 - Virtual decision conference to develop a shared model 2 on non-clinical value aspects to calculate a non-clinical value score for each treatment (and taking into account the aspects' relevance).

Overview of NSCLC and TLV case studies

Case studies agenda

INAMI

NSCLC:

- Web-questionnaire from February 26th to March 2nd
- Virtual decision conference on March 4th

SMA:

- Web-questionnaire from March 26th to 30th
- Virtual decision conference on March 31st

TLV

NSCLC:

- Web-questionnaire from April 12th to April 16th
- Virtual decision conference on April 19th

SMA:

- Web-questionnaire from April 12th to April 16th
- Virtual decision conference on April 20th

Delphi-MACBETH collaborative value modelling framework for treatments' evaluation

TLV virtual decision conference screen

Add print screen com
todos os membros p tlv e
inami, voting e wisdom

INAMI virtual decision conference screen

Add print screen com
todos os membros p tlv e
inami, voting e wisdom

INAMI second line non-small cell lung cancer case (NSCLC)

Overview of the case study

- This case study with INAMI aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects.
 - Web-questionnaire (from February 26th to March 2nd) to collect individual value judgments about three immunotherapy treatments (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), on a small set of key clinical value aspects.
 - Preparation of prototype model: group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited, and value scores for the treatments and relative weights for the clinical value aspects were derived applying decision majority rules.
 - Virtual decision conference (March 4th) to develop a shared multicriteria model based on group discussion of the prototype. Application of the model to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.

Disease Context 1. Indication expansion within existing indication (or across indication within therapeutic indication), for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo line of treatment for the case of metastatic prostate cancer.

Essential	<p>A - Severity of the disease</p> <p>B - Unmet need of the disease</p> <p>C - Medicine's impact on mortality</p> <p>D - Medicine's impact on morbidity</p> <p>E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life</p> <p>F - Medicine's adverse events profile</p> <p>G - Medicine's tolerability to patients</p> <p>J - Medicine's economic impact</p> <p>K - Medicine's affordability</p> <p>L - Medicine's efficiency</p> <p>M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials</p> <p>S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p>
Influential	<p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)</p>
Complementary	<p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	-

■ ▾ INAMI value aspects (NSCLC)

■ ▾ Clinical value aspects

- Impact on mortality (Essential)
- Impact on morbidity (Essential)
- Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)
- Adverse events profile (Essential)
- Tolerability to patients (Essential)
- Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life (Essential)
- Medicines' impact on patient functionality (Complementary)
- Medicine's time for treatment effect (Complementary)
- Medicine's value as a bridge therapy (Influential)
- Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (Influential)

■ Medicine's efficiency (Essential)

■ ▾ Non-clinical value aspects

- Medicine's mechanism of action (Complementary)
- Medicine's ease and convenience for patients (Influential)
- Disease frequency (e.g. rarity) (Complementary)
- Severity of the disease (Essential)
- Medicine's economic impact (Essential)
- Medicine's affordability (Essential)
- Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (Essential)
- Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary)
- Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (Complementary)
- Unmet need of the disease (Essential)
- Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (Complementary)
- Medicine's spill-over effects (Complementary)

At this stage, considering only the clinical value aspects

Clinical value aspects included in the Web-questionnaire and Virtual decision conference

Clinical value aspects	Value aspects selected for Web-questionnaire and decision conference	Justification
Medicine's impact on mortality	Green	
Medicine's adverse events profile		
Medicine's impact on morbidity		
Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	Red	No data available.
Medicines' impact on patient functionality	Red	No data available. This aspect would most probably be partially captured/addressed by the combination of the rest value aspects. Actually we could include "Patients with Adverse events leading to withdrawal from treatment, %" as an indicator for the tolerability aspect!
Medicine's tolerability to patients	Green	
Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Green	
Medicine's time for treatment effect	Red	No data available. This aspect would not be relevant for this therapeutic area.
Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Red	No data available. Not sure if relevant for this disease indication.
Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Red	This aspect would most probably be No data available. I would suspect that given the similar type of technologies, treatments would have an equal performance.

- Clinical value aspects
 - Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - Impact on morbidity (Essential)
 - Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)
 - Adverse events profile (Essential)
 - Tolerability to patients (Essential)

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicators:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median Overall Survival (OS), months • Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective response (i.e. best overall response)
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median duration of response, months
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 Adverse Events (AEs), %
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Adverse Events (AEs) leading to treatment withdrawal, %

Example of the Web-questionnaire screen for 'Impact on mortality'

IMPACT-HTA - NSCLC | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
with two performance indicators: median Overall Survival (OS), months, and Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
<p>... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 - 9.2) = median difference +3 months Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 - 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 - 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 - 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

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Prototype multicriteria value model
based on the results of the
Web-questionnaire

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality' based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity' based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)' based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile' based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients' based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Relative weights for the value aspects derived from group majority judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#2	#3	#4
		100	79.17	66.67	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.17	100	100	75	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.17	100	75	25	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)	0.22	100	50	75	0
Adverse events profile (Essential)	0.28	100	80	60	0
Tolerability to patients (Essential)	0.17	100	100	100	0

**Results of the Virtual decision
conference: enhancement of the
prototype model**

Values scores derived from the Virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Value scores derived from the Virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Values scores derived from the Virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Values scores derived from the Virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Values scores derived from the Virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#3	#2	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		100	64.77	67.61	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.14	100	100	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.14	100	100	25	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)	0.23	100	25	62.5	0
Adverse events profile (Essential)	0.36	100	50	62.5	0
Tolerability to patients (Essential)	0.14	100	100	100	0

INAMI spinal muscular atrophy case (SMA)

Overview of the case study

- This case study with INAMI aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects. (Model 1)
 - Web-questionnaire (March 26th to 30th): 8 participants expressed individual qualitative value judgments for three SMA treatments (Zolgensma, Spinraza and Evrysdi) relatively to a Best Supportive Care, based on clinical evidence, on four clinical value aspects (Impact on mortality, Impact on morbidity, Adverse events profile, Tolerability to patients).
 - Preparation of prototype model 1: group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited, and value scores for the treatments and relative weights for the clinical value aspects were derived applying decision majority rules.
 - Virtual decision conference (March 31st part I): development of a shared model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype. Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.
- Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects. (Model 2)
 - Virtual decision conference (March 31st part II): Development of a shared model 2 on non-clinical value aspects. Application of model 2 to calculate a non-clinical value score for each treatment.

Disease Context 2. Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy.

Essential	<p>A - Severity of the disease</p> <p>B - Unmet need of the disease</p> <p>C - Medicine's impact on mortality</p> <p>D - Medicine's impact on morbidity</p> <p>E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life</p> <p>F - Medicine's adverse events profile</p> <p>J - Medicine's economic impact</p> <p>K - Medicine's affordability</p> <p>L - Medicine's efficiency</p> <p>S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)</p> <p>U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)</p>
Influential	<p>G - Medicine's tolerability to patients</p> <p>M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials</p> <p>N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p> <p>Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality</p> <p>R - Medicine's time for treatment effect</p> <p>T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)</p>
Complementary	<p>H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients</p> <p>I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community</p> <p>O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues</p> <p>P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy</p> <p>V - Medicine's spill-over effects</p> <p>W - Medicine's mechanism of action</p>
Irrelevant	-

INAMI value aspects (SMA)

Clinical value aspects

- Medicine's impact on mortality (Essential)
- Medicine's adverse events profile (Essential)
- Medicine's impact on morbidity (Essential)
- Medicine's tolerability to patients (Influential)
- Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life (Essential)
- Medicines' impact on patient functionality (Influential)
- Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)
- Medicine's time for treatment effect (Influential)
- Medicine's value as a bridge therapy (Complementary)
- Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (Influential)

Clinical value aspects considered in the web-questionnaire in this specific case-study.

Non-clinical value aspects

- Medicine's efficiency (Essential)
- Medicines's mechanism of action (Complementary)
- Medicine's ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)
- Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Influential)
- Disease frequency (e.g. rarity) (Essential)
- Severity of the disease (Essential)
- Medicine's economic impact (Essential)
- Medicine's affordability (Essential)
- Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (Influential)
- Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (Complementary)
- Unmet need of the disease (Essential)
- Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (Complementary)
- Medicine's spill-over effects (Complementary)

Non-clinical value aspects considered in this specific case-study.

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event-free survival, % of patients
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicators:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation

Example of the Web-questionnaire screen for 'Impact on mortality'

IMPACT-HTA | INAMI - SMA FINAL RESULTS | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
 Performance indicator: Event-free survival, % of patients

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
... between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zolgensma 93% event-free survival (STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +61% 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
... between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spinraza 61% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +29% 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
... between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evrysdi 85% event-free survival (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +53% 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

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Prototype multicriteria value model
based on the results of the
Web-questionnaire

Value scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Values scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Value scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Value scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the value aspects derived from group majority judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evryski	Best Supportive Care
		#2	#3	#1	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		94.67	49.33	100	0
Impact on mortality(Essential)	0.33	100	80	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.27	100	75	100	0
Adverse events profile (Essential)	0.13	100	-100	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Influential)	0.27	80	60	100	0

- Results of the virtual decision conference:
- Enhancement of the prototype model 1
 - Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators that emerged from the virtual decision conference

Clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event-free survival, % of patients
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicators:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation
Health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients able to feed orally and did not require nutritional support, %

- ‘Adverse events profile’ value aspect was eliminated since participants considered there was no difference in judgement between all three treatments and the comparator.
- A new value aspect was added: ‘Health related quality of life’
- During the virtual decision conference, the indicator of the ‘Tolerability to patients’ value aspect was modified.

values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

Relative weights for the clinical aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	Best Supportive Care
		#2	#3	#1	#4
CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		90	63.22	100	0
Health Related Quality of life (Essential)	0.25	100	42.86	100	0
Impact on mortality(Essential)	0.36	100	85	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.14	100	50	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Influential)	0.25	60	60	100	0

- Results of the virtual decision conference:
- Enhancement of the prototype model 1
 - Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Medicine's ease and convenience for patients'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Mechanism of action'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Relative weights for the non-clinical value aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Non-clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Evrysdi	Spinraza
		#1	#2	#3
NON-CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		91.67	60	0
Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)	0.70	100	50	0
Mechanism of action (Complementary)	0.25	100	0	0
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Influential)	0.05	66.67	100	0

TLV second line non-small cell lung cancer case (NSCLC)

Overview of the case study

- This case study with TLV aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist health insurers and HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects.
 - Web-questionnaire (from April 12th to 16th) to collect individual value judgments about three immunotherapy treatments (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), on a small set of key clinical value aspects.
 - Preparation of prototype model 1: group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited, and value scores for the treatments and relative weights for the clinical value aspects were derived applying decision majority rules.
 - virtual decision conference (April 19th): development of a shared model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype. Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.

1. Malignant neoplasm metastases (ICD-10 code: O2D), e.g. metastatic castrate resistant prostate cancer.

Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">A - Severity of the diseaseC - Medicine's impact on mortalityE - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of lifeJ - Medicine's economic impactL - Medicine's efficiency
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">B - Unmet need of the diseaseD - Medicine's impact on morbidityK - Medicine's affordabilityM - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trialsR - Medicine's time for treatment effectS - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)W - Risk of leakage across indications
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none">F - Medicine's adverse events profileG - Medicine's tolerability to patientsH - Medicine's ease and convenience for patientsN - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of careO - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issuesP - Medicine's value as a bridge therapyQ - Medicines' impact on patient functionalityT - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)U - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
Irrelevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none">I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the communityX - Risk of drug addiction and its severity

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Clinical value aspects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential) ▣ Impact on morbidity (Influential) ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential) ▣ Adverse events profile (Complementary) ▣ Tolerability to patients (Complementary) ▣ Impact on health related quality of life (Essential) ▣ Impact on patient functionality (Complementary) ▣ Duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)(Complementary) ▣ Time for treatment effect (Influential) ▣ Value as a bridge therapy (Complementary) ▣ Risk of leakage across indications (Influential) ▣ Non-clinical value aspects <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▣ Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary) ▣ Size of patient population (e.g. rarity) (Complementary) ▣ Severity of the disease (Essential) ▣ Medicine's economic impact (Essential) ▣ Medicine's affordability (Influential) ▣ Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (Influential) ▣ Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary) ▣ Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (Complementary) ▣ Unmet need of the disease (Influential) ▣ Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (Irrelevant) ▣ Risk of leakage across indications (Complementary) ▣ Risk of drug addiction and its severity (Irrelevant) ▣ Medicine's efficiency (Essential)

Clinical value aspects considered in the web-questionnaire in this specific case-study.

At this stage, considering only the clinical value aspects

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical aspects	Description
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median Overall Survival (OS), months • Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective response (i.e. best overall response)
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median duration of response, months
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 Adverse Events (AEs), %
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Adverse Events (AEs) leading to treatment withdrawal, %

Example of the Web-questionnaire screen for 'Impact on mortality'

IMPACT-HTA - NSCLC | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
with two performance indicators: median Overall Survival (OS), months, and Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
<p>... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 - 9.2) = median difference +3 months Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 - 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 - 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 - 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

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Prototype multicriteria value model
based on the results of the
Web-questionnaire

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#2	#3	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		95	80	75	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.20	75	100	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Influential)	0.20	100	75	50	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)	0.20	100	50	75	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.20	100	75	75	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.20	100	100	75	0

**Results of the virtual decision
conference: enhancement of the
prototype model**

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#2	#3	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		97.5	60.63	52.03	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.34	100	100	75	0
Impact on morbidity (Influential)	0.25	100	60	20	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)	0.22	100	12.5	37.5	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.13	100	50	50	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.06	60	60	100	0

TLV spinal muscular atrophy case (SMA)

Overview of the case study

- This case study with TLV aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist health insurers and HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects.
 - Web-questionnaire (from April 12th to 16th) to collect individual value judgments about three immunotherapy treatments (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), on a small set of key clinical value aspects.
 - Preparation of prototype model 1: group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited, and value scores for the treatments and relative weights for the clinical value aspects were derived applying decision majority rules.
 - virtual decision conference (April 20th): development of a shared model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype. Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.
- Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects. (Model 2)
 - Proposition of a structure for model 2: including treatment efficiency (measured by an adjusted ICER) and non-clinical value aspects.
 - virtual decision conference (April 20th part II): Development of a shared model 2 on non-clinical value aspects. Application of model 2 to calculate a non-clinical value score for each treatment.

2. Motor neuron diseases and related disorders (ICD-10 code: 08B), e.g. spinal muscular atrophy.

Essential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">A - Severity of the diseaseC - Medicine's impact on mortalityD - Medicine's impact on morbidityE - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of lifeL - Medicine's efficiencyQ - Medicines' impact on patient functionalityU - Size of patient population (i.e. rarity)V - Risk of leakage within licensed indication
Influential	<ul style="list-style-type: none">B - Unmet need of the diseaseJ - Medicine's economic impactK - Medicine's affordabilityM - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trialsR - Medicine's time for treatment effectS - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)W - Risk of leakage across indications
Complementary	<ul style="list-style-type: none">F - Medicine's adverse events profileG - Medicine's tolerability to patientsH - Medicine's ease and convenience for patientsN - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of careO - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issuesP - Medicine's value as a bridge therapyT - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)
Irrelevant	<ul style="list-style-type: none">I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the communityX - Risk of drug addiction and its severity

▣ Clinical value aspects

- ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
- ▣ Impact on morbidity (Essential)
- ▣ Impact on health related quality of life (Essential)
- ▣ Adverse events profile (Complementary)
- ▣ Tolerability to patients (Complementary)
- ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)
- ▣ Impact on patient functionality (Essential)
- ▣ Time for treatment effect (Influential)
- ▣ Value as a bridge therapy (Complementary)
- ▣ Duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (Complementary)
- ▣ Risk of leakage across indications (Influential)

Clinical value aspects considered in the web-questionnaire in this specific case-study.

▣ Non-clinical value aspects

- ▣ Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)
- ▣ Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary)
- ▣ Size of patient population (e.g. rarity) (Essential)
- ▣ Severity of the disease (Essential)
- ▣ Medicine's economic impact (Influential)
- ▣ Medicine's affordability (Influential)
- ▣ Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (Influential)
- ▣ Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (Complementary)
- ▣ Unmet need of the disease (Influential)
- ▣ Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (Irrelevant))
- ▣ Risk of leakage within licensed indication (Essential)
- ▣ Risk of drug addiction and its severity (Irrelevant)

Non-clinical value aspects considered in this specific case-study.

▣ Medicine's efficiency (Essential)

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event-free survival, % of patients
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %
Impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients able to feed orally without nutritional support, %
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation

Non-clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Non-clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
<p>Ease and convenience for patients</p>	<p>Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration</p> <p><u>Indicator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combination of the delivery system and the posology (i.e. dosing)
<p>Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p>	<p>The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).</p> <p><u>Indicators:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for specialised hospital setting

Example of the Web-questionnaire screen for 'Impact on mortality'

IMPACT-HTA || TLV - SMA | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
 Performance indicator: Event-free survival, % of patients

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking Into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
... between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: • Zolgensma 93% event-free survival (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +61%	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
... between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: • Spinraza 61% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +29%	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
... between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: • Evrysdi 85% event-free survival (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +53%	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

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Prototype multicriteria value model
based on the results of the
Web-questionnaire

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
		#1	#2	#3	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		93.33	86.67	80	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.33	100	80	60	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.20	100	66.67	100	0
Health Related Quality of life (Essential)	0.27	75	100	75	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.07	100	100	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.13	100	100	100	0

- Results of the virtual decision conference:
- Enhancement of the prototype model 1
 - Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
		#1	#3	#2	-
CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		97.56	38.66	90.85	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.29	100	55	87.5	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.22	100	37.5	75	0
Health Related Quality of life (Essential)	0.32	100	37.5	100	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.05	100	-100	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.12	80	60	100	0

- Results of the virtual decision conference:
- Enhancement of the prototype model 1
 - Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Ease and convenience for patients'

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Relative weights for the non-clinical value aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Non-clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
		#1	#3	#2	-
+ NON-CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		92.73	0	60.23	-
Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)	0.64	100	0	37.5	-
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary)	0.36	80	0	100	-

WP7, Task 3, Supplementary material No. 3

IMPACT-HTA case study with TLV: Second line Non-Small Cell Lung Cancer (NSCLC)

Results of the two-step interactive process:
Web-questionnaire and virtual decision conference

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April 2021

Overview of the case study

- This case study with TLV aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist health insurers and HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects.
 - Web-questionnaire (from April 12th to 16th) to collect individual value judgments about three immunotherapy treatments (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), on a small set of key clinical value aspects.
 - Preparation of prototype model 1: group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited, and value scores for the treatments and relative weights for the clinical value aspects were derived applying decision majority rules.
 - virtual decision conference (April 19th): development of a shared model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype. Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.

This document summarizes the results from the case study evaluating the clinical results of second line non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) treatments at TLV

Value aspects considered at the beginning of the case study and respective evidence and descriptors of performance

TLV orientations vs clinical aspects considered at the beginning of the case study

Clinical value aspects and their relevance for TLV for the second line non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), as set by the TLV agency

Clinical value aspects specifically considered in modelling in this case-study.

IMPACT TLV NSCLC model 1 GENERAL criado em 04/13/2021

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Influential)
 - ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Complementary)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Complementary)
 - ▣ Impact on health related quality of life (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on patient functionality (Complementary)
 - ▣ Duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)(Complementary)
 - ▣ Time for treatment effect (Influential)
 - ▣ Value as a bridge therapy (Complementary)
 - ▣ Risk of leakage across indications (Influential)

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Influential)
 - ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Complementary)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Complementary)

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical aspects	Description
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median Overall Survival (OS), months • Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective response (i.e. best overall response)
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median duration of response, months
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 Adverse Events (AEs), %
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Adverse Events (AEs) leading to treatment withdrawal, %

Description of 'Impact on mortality'

Description

Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.

Indicators

- Median Overall Survival (OS), months
- Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 – 9.2) = median difference +3 months

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78)

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 – 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 – 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 – 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006)

Description of 'Impact on morbidity'

Description

Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease).

Indicators

- Objective response (i.e. best overall response)

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 20% objective response vs Docetaxel 11% objective response = difference +9%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 18% objective response vs Docetaxel 9% objective response = difference +9%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 15% objective response vs Docetaxel 13% objective response = difference +2%

Description of 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Description

Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration).

Indicators

- Median duration of response, months

Clinical evidence on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab median duration of response 19.9 months (95% CI, 11.4-30.8) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 5.6 months (95% CI, 4.4 – 7.0) = median difference +14.3 months

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab median duration of response not reached (95% CI, 4.2-10.5) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6 months (95% CI, 2.7 – 6.1)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab median duration of response 16.3 months (95% CI, 10-Not reached) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6.2 months (95% CI, 4.9 – 7.6) = median difference +10.1 months

Description of 'Adverse events profile'

Description

The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.

Indicators

- Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 Adverse Events (AEs), %

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 10% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 55% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -45%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 15 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 35% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -20%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, minimum 26 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 15% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 42% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -28%

Description of 'Tolerability to patients'

Description

The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.

Indicators

- Patients with Adverse Events (AEs) leading to treatment withdrawal, %

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 6% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 13% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -7%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 6% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 12% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -6%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 21 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 8% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 18% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -10%

Prototype multicriteria value model based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Overview of the Web-questionnaire (April 12th to 16th)

- Qualitative value judgments were elicited on five key value clinical aspects.
- 5 participants expressed judgments about the three immunotherapy treatments of interest (Nivolumab, Pembrolizumab and Atezolizumab), relatively to a comparator chemotherapy (Docetaxel), based on clinical evidence.
- At the end, group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited.
- A prototype multicriteria value model was built with value scores for the treatments and relative weights, for the five clinical value aspects, derived from the group judgments.

Welphi screen

IMPACT-HTA | TLV- NSCLC | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
with two performance indicators: median Overall Survival (OS), months, and Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
<p>... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 - 9.2) = median difference +3 months Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 - 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 - 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 - 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

← BACK NEXT →

5 participants answered to the web-questionnaire.

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 – 9.2) = median difference +3 months

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78)

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 – 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 – 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 – 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006)

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

	very weak	weak	moderate	Strong	very strong	extreme
... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	50%	25%	25%	0%
... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	25%	50%	25%	0%
... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	25%	50%	25%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 20% objective response vs Docetaxel 11% objective response = difference +9%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 18% objective response vs Docetaxel 9% objective response = difference +9%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 15% objective response vs Docetaxel 13% objective response = difference +2%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme
... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	25%	75%	0%	0%
... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	75%	25%	0%	0%
... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	75%	25%	0%	0%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Clinical evidence on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab median duration of response 19.9 months (95% CI, 11.4-30.8) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 5.6 months (95% CI, 4.4 – 7.0) = median difference +14.3 months

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab median duration of response not reached (95% CI, 4.2-10.5) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6 months (95% CI, 2.7 – 6.1)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab median duration of response 16.3 months (95% CI, 10-Not reached) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6.2 months (95% CI, 4.9 – 7.6) = median difference +10.1 months

Summary of individual judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme
... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	0%	75%	25%	0%
... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	50%	25%	25%	0%	0%
... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	25%	50%	0%	25%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 10% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 55% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -45%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 15 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 35% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -20%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, minimum 26 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 15% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 42% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -28%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme
... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	0%	60%	20%	0%
... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	60%	20%	0%	0%
... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	0%	60%	0%	20%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 6% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 13% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -7%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 6% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 12% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -6%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 21 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 8% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 18% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -10%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme
... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel	0%	25%	25%	50%	0%	0%
... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	25%	25%	50%	0%	0%
... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel	0%	25%	25%	25%	25%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#2	#3	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		95	80	75	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.20	75	100	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Influential)	0.20	100	75	50	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)	0.20	100	50	75	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.20	100	75	75	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.20	100	100	75	0

Results of the virtual decision conference: enhancement of the prototype model

Overview of the virtual decision conference (April 19th)

- Brief presentation of the prototype model for the five clinical aspects.
- Development of a shared multicriteria model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype.
- Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.

Participants of the virtual decision conference

- TLV participants:
 - Andreas Pousette
 - Cecilia Tolin
 - Emma Olin
 - Isak Nilsson
 - Lina Book

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 – 9.2) = median difference +3 months

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78)

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 – 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 – 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 – 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006)

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 20% objective response vs Docetaxel 11% objective response = difference +9%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 18% objective response vs Docetaxel 9% objective response = difference +9%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 15% objective response vs Docetaxel 13% objective response = difference +2%

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Clinical evidence on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab median duration of response 19.9 months (95% CI, 11.4-30.8) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 5.6 months (95% CI, 4.4 – 7.0) = median difference +14.3 months

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab median duration of response not reached (95% CI, 4.2-10.5) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6 months (95% CI, 2.7 – 6.1)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab median duration of response 16.3 months (95% CI, 10-Not reached) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6.2 months (95% CI, 4.9 – 7.6) = median difference +10.1 months

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 10% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 55% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -45%

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... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, minimum 26 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 15% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 42% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -28%

values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years, patients randomised active arm n = 292 and 135 vs control arm n = 290 and 137): Nivolumab 6% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 13% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -7%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months, patients randomised active arm n = 345 vs control arm n = 343): Pembrolizumab 6% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 12% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -6%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 21 months, patients randomised active arm n = 425 vs control arm n = 424): Atezolizumab 8% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 18% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -10%

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#2	#3	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		97.5	60.63	52.03	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.34	100	100	75	0
Impact on morbidity (Influential)	0.25	100	60	20	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)	0.22	100	12.5	37.5	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.13	100	50	50	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.06	60	60	100	0

Clinical overall scores of each treatment

Treatments' profile

Appendix - Comparing the prototype model with the virtual decision conference model

Comparisons with the prototype model: added-value of the treatments

Overall score - comparison between prototype
and model

- In the decision conference (DC), the ranking of the treatments hasn't changed:
 - Prototype and DC: Nivolumab > Pembrolizumab > Atezolizumab

Comparisons with the prototype model: treatments' profile

Atezolizumab

Nivolumab

Comparisons with the prototype model: treatments' profile

WP7, Task 3, Supplementary material No. 4

IMPACT-HTA case study with TLV: Spinal Muscular Atrophy (SMA)

Results of the two-step interactive process:
Web-questionnaire and virtual decision conference

Mónica Oliveira, Carlos Bana e Costa, Ana Vieira, Klára
Dimitrovová (IST, U Lisboa)
Panos Kanavos, Aris Angelis (LSE)

April 2021

Overview of the case study

- This case study with TLV aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist health insurers and HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects.
 - Web-questionnaire (from April 12th to 16th) to collect individual value judgments about three immunotherapy treatments (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), on a small set of key clinical value aspects.
 - Preparation of prototype model 1: group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited, and value scores for the treatments and relative weights for the clinical value aspects were derived applying decision majority rules.
 - virtual decision conference (April 20th): development of a shared model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype. Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.
- Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects. (Model 2)
 - Proposition of a structure for model 2: including treatment efficiency (measured by an adjusted ICER) and non-clinical value aspects.
 - virtual decision conference (April 20th part II): Development of a shared model 2 on non-clinical value aspects. Application of model 2 to calculate a non-clinical value score for each treatment.

This document summarizes the results from the case study evaluating the clinical results of spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) treatments at TLV

Value aspects considered at the beginning of the case study and respective evidence and descriptors of performance

TLV orientations vs clinical aspects considered at the beginning of the case study

Clinical value aspects and their relevance for TLV for the spinal muscular atrophy(SMA), as set by the TLV agency

Clinical value aspects specifically considered in modelling in this case-study.

IMPACT TLV SMA Model 1 General criado em 04/14/2021

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on health related quality of life (Essential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Complementary)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Complementary)
 - ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Influential)
 - ▣ Impact on patient functionality (Essential)
 - ▣ Time for treatment effect (Influential)
 - ▣ Value as a bridge therapy (Complementary)
 - ▣ Duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (Complementary)
 - ▣ Risk of leakage across indications (Influential)

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on health related quality of life (Essential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Complementary)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Complementary)

TLV orientations vs non-clinical aspects considered at the beginning of the case study

Non-clinical value aspects and their relevance for TLV for the spinal muscular atrophy (SMA), as set by the TLV agency

IMPACT TLV SMA Model 2 General criado em 04/14/2021

- Non-clinical value aspects
 - Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)
 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary)
 - Size of patient population (e.g. rarity) (Essential)
 - Severity of the disease (Essential)
 - Medicine's economic impact (Influential)
 - Medicine's affordability (Influential)
 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (Influential)
 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (Complementary)
 - Unmet need of the disease (Influential)
 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (Irrelevant)
 - Risk of leakage within licensed indication (Essential)
 - Risk of drug addiction and its severity (Irrelevant)
- Medicine's efficiency (Essential)

Non-clinical value aspects considered in this specific case-study

- Non-clinical value aspects
 - Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)
 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary)

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event-free survival, % of patients
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %
Impact on health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients able to feed orally without nutritional support, %
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation

Description of 'Impact on mortality'

Description

Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.

Indicators

- Event-free survival, % of patients

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 93% event-free survival (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +61%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 61% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +29%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 85% event-free survival (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +53%

Description of 'Impact on morbidity'

Description

Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease).

Indicators

- Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 37% BSID (at ~10-18 months age, STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +37%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~10% BSID (at ~18 months age, clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +10%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 29% BSID (at ~17 months age, FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +29%

Description of 'Impact on health related quality of life'

Description

Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing.

Indicators

- Patients able to feed orally without nutritional support, %

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 75% able to feed (at ~10-18 months age, STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC ~0% able to feed (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +75%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~25% able to feed (at ~18 months age, clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% able to feed (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +25%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 74% BSID (at ~17 months age, FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +74%

Description of 'Adverse events profile'

Description

The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.

Indicators

- % of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 49% serious AEs (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -7%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 60% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +4%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 51% serious AEs (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -5%

Description of 'Tolerability to patients'

Description

The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.

.

Indicators

% of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 9% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (STRIVE US maximum follow up 18 months, patients randomised n = 22) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -30%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 16% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -23%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 0% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -39%

Background information: Non-clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Non-clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
<p>Ease and convenience for patients</p>	<p>Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration</p> <p><u>Indicator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combination of the delivery system and the posology (i.e. dosing)
<p>Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care</p>	<p>The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).</p> <p><u>Indicators:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for specialised hospital setting

Description of 'Ease and convenience for patients'

Description

Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration.

Indicators

- Combination of the delivery system and the posology (i.e. dosing).

Clinical evidence on 'Ease and convenience for patients'

Zolgensma

One-time IV infusion.

Spinraza

Intrathecally; an induction period (4 loading doses) is followed by life-long repeated intrathecal administrations every 4 months.

Evrysdi

Administered orally once daily.

Description of 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Description

The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).

Indicators

- Need for specialised hospital setting.

Clinical evidence on 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Zolgensma

Provided at high specialist centres. Before administration of onasemnogene abeparvovec, baseline laboratory testing is required, including: AAV9 antibody testing using an appropriately validated assay, liver function: alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and total bilirubin, platelet count, and troponin-I.

Spinraza

Offered primarily at academic medical center. At baseline and prior to each dose, obtain a platelet count, coagulation laboratory testing, and quantitative spot urine protein testing.

Evrysdi

Administered at-home.

Prototype multicriteria value model based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Overview of the Web-questionnaire (April 12th to 16th)

- Qualitative value judgments were elicited on five key value clinical aspects.
- 6 participants expressed judgments about the three SMA treatments (Zolgensma, Spinraza and Evrysdi) relatively to a Best Supportive Care, based on clinical evidence.
- At the end, group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited.
- A prototype multicriteria value model was built with value scores for the treatments and relative weights, for the five clinical value aspects, derived from the group judgments.

Welphi screen

IMPACT-HTA || TLV - SMA | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
 Performance indicator: Event-free survival, % of patients

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
... between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: • Zolgensma 93% event-free survival (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +61%	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
... between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: • Spinraza 61% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +29%	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
... between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care ? Based on the following clinical evidence: • Evrysdi 85% event-free survival (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +53%	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

← BACK NEXT →

6 participants answered to the web-questionnaire.

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 93% event-free survival (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +61%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 61% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +29%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 85% event-free survival (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +53%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	33%	17%	50%	0%	0%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	33%	50%	17%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	50%	17%	33%	0%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 37% BSID (at ~10-18 months age, STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +37%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~10% BSID (at ~18 months age, clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +10%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 29% BSID (at ~17 months age, FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +29%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	50%	0%	33%	0%	17%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	0%	50%	17%	0%	17%	0%	17%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	50%	0%	33%	0%	17%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 75% able to feed (at ~10-18 months age, STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC ~0% able to feed (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +75%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~25% able to feed (at ~18 months age, clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% able to feed (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +25%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 74% BSID (at ~17 months age, FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +74%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	33%	33%	17%	17%	0%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	0%	17%	33%	50%	0%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	33%	33%	0%	17%	17%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 49% serious AEs (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -7%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 60% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +4%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 51% serious AEs (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -5%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	50%	17%	33%	0%	0%	0%	0%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	50%	17%	33%	0%	0%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	50%	17%	33%	0%	0%	0%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 9% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (STRIVE US maximum follow up 18 months, patients randomised n = 22) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -30%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 16% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -23%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 0% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -39%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	0%	50%	17%	33%	0%	0%	0%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	0%	50%	33%	17%	0%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	0%	50%	0%	33%	17%	0%	0%

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
		#1	#2	#3	#4
▼ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		93.33	86.67	80	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.33	100	80	60	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.20	100	66.67	100	0
Health Related Quality of life (Essential)	0.27	75	100	75	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.07	100	100	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.13	100	100	100	0

Results of the virtual decision conference:

- **Enhancement of the prototype model 1**
- Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2

Overview of the virtual decision conference (April 20th)

- Brief presentation of the prototype model for the five clinical aspects.
- Development of a shared multicriteria model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype.
- Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.
- Development of a shared model 2 on non-clinical value aspects.
- Application of model 2 to calculate a non-clinical value score for each treatment.
- Discussion of the model outputs.

Participants of the virtual decision conference

- TLV participants:
 - Johan Pontén
 - Cecilia Tolin
 - Isak Nilsson
 - Niklas Hedberg
 - Tobias Karlberg

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 93% event-free survival (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +61%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 61% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +29%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 85% event-free survival (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +53%

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 37% BSID (at ~10-18 months age, STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +37%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~10% BSID (at ~18 months age, clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +10%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 29% BSID (at ~17 months age, FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +29%

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 75% able to feed (at ~10-18 months age, STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC ~0% able to feed (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +75%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~25% able to feed (at ~18 months age, clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% able to feed (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +25%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 74% BSID (at ~17 months age, FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC ~0% BSID (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +74%

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 49% serious AEs (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months, patients randomised n = 22 and 32) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -7%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 60% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference +4%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 51% serious AEs (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months, patients randomised n = 41) vs BSC 56% serious AEs (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -5%

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 9% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (STRIVE US maximum follow up 18 months, patients randomised n = 22) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -30%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 16% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 80) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -23%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 0% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 39% AEs leading to treatment discontinuation (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months, patients randomised n = 41) = difference -39%

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
		#1	#3	#2	-
CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		97.56	38.66	90.85	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.29	100	55	87.5	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.22	100	37.5	75	0
Health Related Quality of life (Essential)	0.32	100	37.5	100	0
Adverse events profile (Complementary)	0.05	100	-100	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Complementary)	0.12	80	60	100	0

Clinical overall scores of each treatment

Treatments' profile

Results of the virtual decision conference:

- Enhancement of the prototype model 1
- **Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2**

Clinical evidence on 'Ease and convenience for patients'

Zolgensma

One-time IV infusion.

Spinraza

Intrathecally; an induction period (4 loading doses) is followed by life-long repeated intrathecal administrations every 4 months.

Evrysdi

Administered orally once daily.

Values scores derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Ease and convenience for patients'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Zolgensma

Provided at high specialist centres. Before administration of onasemnogene abeparvovec, baseline laboratory testing is required, including: AAV9 antibody testing using an appropriately validated assay, liver function: alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and total bilirubin, platelet count, and troponin-I.

Spinraza

Offered primarily at academic medical center. At baseline and prior to each dose, obtain a platelet count, coagulation laboratory testing, and quantitative spot urine protein testing.

Evrysdi

Administered at-home.

Values scores derived from group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Relative weights for the non-clinical value aspects derived from the virtual decision conference group qualitative judgments

Non-clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
		#1	#3	#2	-
+ NON-CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		92.73	0	60.23	-
Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)	0.64	100	0	37.5	-
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Complementary)	0.36	80	0	100	-

Non-clinical overall scores of each treatment

Appendix – Analyzing clinical and non-clinical treatments value

What-if analysis on clinical value aspects

Graph x-y

Treatments with higher clinical and non-clinical value scores

	Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
Total cost of treatment with the drug (annual)	£ 1,795,000	£ 450 000,00	£ 100 288,80	£ 570,00

WP7, Task 3, Supplementary material No. 5

IMPACT-HTA case study with INAMI: second line non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)

Results of the two-step interactive process:
Web-questionnaire and decision conference

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April 2021

Overview of the case study

- This case study with INAMI aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist health insurers and HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- It consisted on a two-step interactive process that involved:
 - a Web-questionnaire (from February 26th to March 2nd) to collect individual value judgments about three immunotherapy treatments (nivolumab, pembrolizumab and atezolizumab), relative to a comparator chemotherapy (docetaxel), on a small set of key clinical value aspects.
 - a group decision conference (March 4th) to develop a shared multicriteria model and discuss its outputs.
- Based on the Web-questionnaire a prototype multicriteria value model was built.
- In the decision conference, a shared multicriteria model for the five clinical aspects was developed by enhancing the prototype model.

This document summarizes the results from the case study evaluating the clinical results of second line non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) treatments at INAMI

Value aspects considered at the beginning of the case study and respective evidence and descriptors of performance

INAMI orientations vs clinical aspects considered at the beginning of the case study

Clinical value aspects and their relevance for INAMI for the second line non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), as set by the INAMI agency

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Essential)
 - ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Essential)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Essential)
 - ▣ Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life (Essential)
 - ▣ Medicines' impact on patient functionality (Complementary)
 - ▣ Medicine's time for treatment effect (Complementary)
 - ▣ Medicine's value as a bridge therapy (Influential)
 - ▣ Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s) (Influential)

Clinical value aspects specifically considered in modelling in this case-study.

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Essential)
 - ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Essential)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Essential)

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicators:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median Overall Survival (OS), months • Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objective response (i.e. best overall response)
Duration of treatment effect(s)	Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration). <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Median duration of response, months
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 Adverse Events (AEs), %
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients with Adverse Events (AEs) leading to treatment withdrawal, %

Description of 'Impact on mortality'

Description

Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.

Indicators

- Median Overall Survival (OS), months
- Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 – 9.2) = median difference +3 months

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78)

...between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 – 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, $p < 0.0001$)

...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 – 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 – 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, $p = 0.0006$)

Description of 'Impact on morbidity'

Description

Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease).

Indicators

- Objective response (i.e. best overall response)

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab 20% objective response vs Docetaxel 11% objective response = difference +9%

...between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months): Pembrolizumab 18% objective response vs Docetaxel 9% objective response = difference +9%

...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab 15% objective response vs Docetaxel 13% objective response = difference +2%

Description of 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Description

Time duration of medicine's beneficial effect(s) (e.g. short effect duration vs long effect duration).

Indicators

- Median duration of response, months

Clinical evidence on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab median duration of response 19.9 months (95% CI, 11.4-30.8) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 5.6 months (95% CI, 4.4 – 7.0) = median difference +14.3 months

...between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months): Pembrolizumab median duration of response not reached (95% CI, 4.2-10.5) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6 months (95% CI, 2.7 – 6.1)

...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab median duration of response 16.3 months (95% CI, 10-Not reached) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6.2 months (95% CI, 4.9 – 7.6) = median difference +10.1 months

Description of 'Adverse events profile'

Description

The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.

Indicators

- Patients with Treatment-related Grade 3,4 Adverse Events (AEs), %

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years): Nivolumab 10 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 55% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -45%

...between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab 15 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 35% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -20%

...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, minimum 26 months): Atezolizumab 15 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 42% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -28%

Description of 'Tolerability to patients'

Description

The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.

Indicators

- Patients with Adverse Events (AEs) leading to treatment withdrawal, %

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years): Nivolumab 6 % AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 13% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -7%

...between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab 6 % AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 12% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -6%

...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 21 months): Atezolizumab 8% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 18% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -10%

Prototype multicriteria value model based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Overview of the Web-questionnaire (February 26th to March 2nd)

- Qualitative value judgments were elicited on five key value clinical aspects.
- Nine participants expressed judgments about the three immunotherapy treatments of interest (Nivolumab, Pembrolizumab and Atezolizumab), relatively to a comparator chemotherapy (Docetaxel), based on clinical evidence.
- At the end, group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited.
- A prototype multicriteria value model was built with value scores for the treatments and relative weights, for the five clinical value aspects, derived from the group judgments.

Welphi screen

IMPACT-HTA - NSCLC | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
with two performance indicators: median Overall Survival (OS), months, and Overall Survival (OS) Hazard Ratio (HR)

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
<p>... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 - 9.2) = median difference +3 months Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 - 9.5) = median difference +3.4 months Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab median OS 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 - 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6 months (95% CI, 8.6 - 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006) 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

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9 participants answered to the web-questionnaire.

Summary of evidence and individual judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months):
 Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs
 Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 – 9.2) = median
 difference +3 months

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months):
 Nivolumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.68 (95% CI, 0.59-0.78)

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab
 median OS 11.8 months (95% CI, 10.4-13.1) vs Docetaxel median
 OS 8.4 months (95% CI, 7.6 – 9.5) = median difference +3.4
 months

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab vs
 Docetaxel OS HR = 0.69 (95% CI, 0.60-0.80, p<0.0001)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab median OS
 13.8 months (95% CI, 11.8 – 15.7) vs Docetaxel median OS 9.6
 months (95% CI, 8.6 – 11.2) = median difference +4.2 months

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab vs
 Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, p=0.0006)

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Strong

Choice rule 2: select two consecutive judgments with highest majority over 50%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Strong

Choice rule 2: select two consecutive judgments with highest majority over 50%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate

Choice rule 1: select judgment with more than 50%

Values scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months):
Nivolumab 20% objective response vs Docetaxel 11% objective response = difference +9%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months): Pembrolizumab 18% objective response vs Docetaxel 9% objective response = difference +9%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab 15% objective response vs Docetaxel 13% objective response = difference +2%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Strong

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Very weak

Values scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Summary of individual judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months):
Nivolumab median duration of response 19.9 months (95% CI, 11.4-30.8) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 5.6 months (95% CI, 4.4 – 7.0) = median difference +14.3 months

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months): Pembrolizumab median duration of response not reached (95% CI, 4.2-10.5) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6 months (95% CI, 2.7 – 6.1)

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab median duration of response 16.3 months (95% CI, 10-Not reached) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 6.2 months (95% CI, 4.9 – 7.6) = median difference +10.1 months

Summary of individual judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Strong-Very strong

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Weak-Moderate

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Strong

Values scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Summary of individual judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years):
Nivolumab 10 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel
55% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -45%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab 15
% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 35% Treatment-
related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -20%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, minimum 26 months):
Atezolizumab 15 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel
42% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -28%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Very strong

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Strong-Very strong

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Very strong

Choice rule 3: if rule 2 not enough to choose, select three consecutive judgments

Values scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Summary of individual judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years): Nivolumab 6 % AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 13% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -7%

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 42.6 months): Pembrolizumab 6 % AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 12% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -6%

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 21 months): Atezolizumab 8% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 18% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -10%

Summary of individual judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

... between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Strong

... between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Strong

... between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

Group majority judgment:

Moderate-Strong

Values scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the value aspects derived from group majority judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#2	#3	#4
		100	79.17	66.67	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.17	100	100	75	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.17	100	75	25	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)	0.22	100	50	75	0
Adverse events profile (Essential)	0.28	100	80	60	0
Tolerability to patients (Essential)	0.17	100	100	100	0

Treatments' profile

Results of the decision conference: enhancement of the prototype model

Overview of the decision conference (March 4th)

- Presentation of the prototype model for the five clinical aspects.
- Development of a shared multicriteria model for the five clinical aspects, by enhancing the prototype model.
- Discussion of the model outputs and what-if analysis.

Participants of the decision conference

- INAMI participants:
 - Barbara Claus
 - Caroline Lebbe
 - Diane Kleinermans
 - Joël Daems
 - Lisa Vervueren
 - Maëlle Anciaux
 - Marc Van De Castele
 - Piet Vancraeynest
 - Pol Specenier
 - Simon Roels

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab median OS 11.1 months (95% CI, 9.2-13.1) vs Docetaxel median OS 8.1 months (95% CI, 7.2 – 9.2) = median difference +3 months

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...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

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OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab vs Docetaxel OS HR = 0.75 (95% CI, 0.64-0.89, $p = 0.0006$)

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab 20% objective response vs Docetaxel 11% objective response = difference +9%

...between Pembrolizumab and Docetaxel

Keynote 010 (median follow up 13.1 months): Pembrolizumab 18% objective response vs Docetaxel 9% objective response = difference +9%

...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months): Atezolizumab 15% objective response vs Docetaxel 13% objective response = difference +2%

Value scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Clinical evidence on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (median follow up 69.5 months): Nivolumab median duration of response 19.9 months (95% CI, 11.4-30.8) vs Docetaxel median duration of response 5.6 months (95% CI, 4.4 – 7.0) = median difference +14.3 months

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Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Duration of treatment effect(s)'

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years): Nivolumab 10 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 55% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -45%

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...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 28 months, minimum 26 months): Atezolizumab 15 % Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs vs Docetaxel 42% Treatment-related Grade 3,4 AEs = difference -28%

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Nivolumab and Docetaxel

Checkmate 057 and 017 (minimum follow up 2 years): Nivolumab 6 % AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 13% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -7%

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...between Atezolizumab and Docetaxel

OAK (median follow up 21 months): Atezolizumab 8% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal vs Docetaxel 18% AEs leading to treatment withdrawal = difference -10%

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the aspects derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Nivolumab	Pembrolizumab	Atezolizumab	Docetaxel
		#1	#3	#2	#4
▾ CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		100	64.77	67.61	0
Impact on mortality (Essential)	0.14	100	100	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.14	100	100	25	0
Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)	0.23	100	25	62.5	0
Adverse events profile (Essential)	0.36	100	50	62.5	0
Tolerability to patients (Essential)	0.14	100	100	100	0

Treatments' profile

What-if analysis on weights: added-value of the treatments for a different set of weights

- There were no significant changes on the added-value of the treatments when changing the highlighted judgement (from moderate to strong).

What-if analysis on 'Adverse events profile' value aspect

- 'Adverse events profile' has a weight of 36% - to change the ranking of the treatments, this weight has to be decreased by more than 15%.

Appendix - Comparing the prototype model with the decision conference model

Comparisons with the prototype model: added-value of the treatments

- In the decision conference (DC), the ranking of the treatments has changed:
 - Prototype: Nivolumab > Pembrolizumab > Atezolizumab
 - DC: Nivolumab > Atezolizumab > Pembrolizumab

Comparisons with the prototype model: treatments' profile

Atezolizumab

Pembrolizumab

WP7, Task 3, Supplementary material No. 6

IMPACT-HTA case study with INAMI: spinal muscular atrophy (SMA)

Results of the two-step interactive process:
Web-questionnaire and decision conference

Mónica Oliveira, Carlos Bana e Costa, Ana Vieira, Klára
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April 2021

Overview of the case study

- This case study with INAMI aimed at testing a new multicriteria framework to assist HTA agencies in evaluating new treatments on multiple value aspects.
- Model building for treatments' evaluation on clinical value aspects. (Model 1)
 - Web-questionnaire (March 26th to 30th): 8 participants expressed individual qualitative value judgments for three SMA treatments (Zolgensma, Spinraza and Evrysdi) relatively to a Best Supportive Care, based on clinical evidence, on four clinical value aspects (Impact on mortality, Impact on morbidity, Adverse events profile, Tolerability to patients).
 - Preparation of prototype model 1: group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited, and value scores for the treatments and relative weights for the clinical value aspects were derived applying decision majority rules.
 - Decision conference (March 31st part I): development of a shared model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype. Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.
- Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects. (Model 2)
 - Decision conference (March 31st part II): Development of a shared model 2 on non-clinical value aspects. Application of model 2 to calculate a non-clinical value score for each treatment.

This document summarizes the results from the case study evaluating the clinical and non-clinical results of spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) treatments at INAMI

Value aspects considered at the beginning of the case study and respective evidence and descriptors of performance

INAMI orientations vs clinical aspects considered at the beginning of the case study

Clinical value aspects and their relevance for INAMI for the spinal muscular atrophy (SMA), as set by the INAMI agency

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Essential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Essential)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Influential)
 - ▣ Impact on health-related quality of life (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on patient functionality (Influential)
 - ▣ Duration of treatment effect(s) (Essential)
 - ▣ Time for treatment effect (Influential)
 - ▣ Value as a bridge therapy (Complementary)
 - ▣ Duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)(Influential)

Clinical value aspects considered in the web-questionnaire in this specific case-study

- ▣ Clinical value aspects
 - ▣ Impact on mortality (Essential)
 - ▣ Impact on morbidity (Essential)
 - ▣ Adverse events profile (Essential)
 - ▣ Tolerability to patients (Influential)

INAMI orientations vs non-clinical aspects considered at the beginning of the case study

Non-clinical value aspects and their relevance for INAMI for the spinal muscular atrophy (SMA), as set by the INAMI agency

- Non-clinical value aspects
 - Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)
 - Mechanism of action (Complementary)
 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Influential)
 - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity) (Essential)
 - Severity of the disease (Essential)
 - Medicine's economic impact (Essential)
 - Medicine's affordability (Essential)
 - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials (Influential)
 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues (Complementary)
 - Unmet need of the disease (Essential)
 - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community (Complementary)
 - Medicine's spill-over effects (Complementary)
- Treatment's efficiency (Essential)

Non-clinical value aspects considered in this specific case-study

- Non-clinical value aspects
 - Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)
 - Mechanism of action (Complementary)
 - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Influential)

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event-free survival, % of patients
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicators:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %
Adverse events profile	The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation

Description of 'Impact on mortality'

Description

Impact of the medicine on life expectancy.

Indicators

- Event-free survival, % of patients

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 93% (STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +61%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 61% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +29%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 85% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +53%

Description of 'Impact on morbidity'

Description

Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease).

Indicators

- Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 37% (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +37%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~10% (clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +10%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 29% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +29%

Description of 'Adverse events profile'

Description

The seriousness and frequency of adverse (unwanted) events due to the treatment is administered to a patient or at some time afterwards.

Indicators

- % of patients experiencing serious AEs (excluding deaths)

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 49% (STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC 56% (clinical assumption) = difference -7%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 60% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 56% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +4%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 51% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 56% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -5%

Description of 'Tolerability to patients'

Description

The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction.

Indicators

- % of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation.

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 9% (STR1VE US maximum follow up 18 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -30%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 16% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -23%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 0% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -39%

Non-clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators

Non-clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	<p>Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration.</p> <p><u>Indicator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Combination of the delivery system and the posology (i.e. dosing).
Mechanism of action	<p>The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).</p> <p><u>Indicators:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The technology's mechanism of action.
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	<p>The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).</p> <p><u>Indicator:</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for specialised hospital setting.

Description of 'Medicine's ease and convenience for patients'

Description

Ease and convenience of medicine's administration, relating to less invasive delivery systems, improved posology due to reduced dosing frequency or duration of administration, or abolition of special administration.

Indicators

- Combination of the delivery system and the posology (i.e. dosing).

Clinical evidence on 'Medicine's ease and convenience for patients'

Zolgensma

One-time IV infusion.

Spinraza

Administered orally once daily.

Evrysdi

Intrathecally; an induction period (4 loading doses) is followed by life-long repeated intrathecal administrations every 4 months.

Description of 'Mechanism of action'

Description

The innovativeness of the medicine's specific biochemical process through which it produces its pharmacological effect (e.g. the specific molecular targets to which the medicine binds, such as an enzyme or receptor).

Indicators

- The technology's mechanism of action.

Clinical evidence on 'Mechanism of action'

Zolgensma

Recombinant AAV9-based gene therapy designed to deliver a copy of the gene encoding the human SMN protein.

Spinraza

Antisense oligonucleotide (ASO) designed to treat SMA caused by mutations in chromosome 5q that lead to SMN protein deficiency.

Evrysdi

Survival of motor neuron 2 (SMN2) splicing modifier designed to treat patients with SMA caused by mutations in chromosome 5q that lead to SMN protein deficiency.

Description of 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Description

The wider impact resulting from the reimbursement and adoption of the medicine on the health care system organisation and delivery, including service, workforce, information and other technology requirements (e.g. need of specialised hospital setting or provision of diagnostic testing).

Indicators

- Need for specialised hospital setting.

Clinical evidence on 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Zolgensma

Provided at high specialist centres. Before administration of onasemnogene abeparvovec, baseline laboratory testing is required, including: AAV9 antibody testing using an appropriately validated assay, liver function: alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and total bilirubin, platelet count, and troponin-I.

Spinraza

Offered primarily at academic medical center. At baseline and prior to each dose, obtain a platelet count, coagulation laboratory testing, and quantitative spot urine protein testing.

Evrysdi

Administered at-home.

Prototype multicriteria value model 1 based on the results of the Web-questionnaire

Overview of the Web-questionnaire (March 26th to 30th)

- Qualitative value judgments were elicited on four key clinical value aspects.
- Eight participants expressed judgments about three SMA treatments (Zolgensma, Spinraza and Evrysdi) relatively to a Best Supportive Care, based on clinical evidence.
- At the end, group majority judgments were derived from the individual judgments elicited.
- A prototype multicriteria value model was built with value scores for the treatments and relative weights, for the four clinical value aspects, derived from the group judgments.

Welphi screen

IMPACT-HTA | INAMI - SMA FINAL RESULTS | Round 1 | Elicitation of value judgments within each aspect

Aspect: Impact on mortality (Relevance for the agency: Essential)
Performance indicator: Event-free survival, % of patients

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer	Comment
Taking into account the relevance of 'Impact on mortality', what is the difference in value ...								
<p>... between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Zolgensma 93% event-free survival (STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +61% 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Spinraza 61% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +29% 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>
<p>... between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care ?</p> <p>Based on the following clinical evidence:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Evrysdi 85% event-free survival (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 32% event-free survival (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +53% 	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input checked="" type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="text"/>

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8 participants answered to the web-questionnaire.

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 93% (STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +61%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 61% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +29%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 85% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +53%

Summary of web-questionnaire individual judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	0%	13%	0%	13%	63%	13%	0%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	13%	88%	0%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	0%	13%	0%	25%	63%	0%	0%

Value scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 37% (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +37%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~10% (clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +10%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 29% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +29%

Summary of web-questionnaire individual judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	0%	13%	0%	38%	25%	25%	0%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	25%	13%	25%	25%	13%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	0%	13%	13%	38%	38%	0%	0%

Values scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Clinical evidence on 'Adverse events profile'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 49% (STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC 56% (clinical assumption) = difference -7%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 60% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 56% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +4%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 51% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 56% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -5%

Summary of web-questionnaire individual judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	13%	75%	0%	0%	0%	13%	0%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	25%	63%	13%	0%	0%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	13%	75%	0%	0%	0%	13%	0%

Value scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Adverse events profile'

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 9% (STR1VE US maximum follow up 18 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -30%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 16% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -23%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 0% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -39%

Summary of web-questionnaire individual judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

	very weak	weak	moderate	strong	very strong	extreme	don't want to answer
...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	38%	38%	13%	0%	13%
...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care	0%	0%	63%	25%	13%	0%	0%
...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care	0%	13%	25%	13%	38%	13%	0%

Value scores derived from group majority judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Relative weights for the value aspects derived from group majority judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evryski	Best Supportive Care
		#2	#3	#1	#4
CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		94.67	49.33	100	0
Impact on mortality(Essential)	0.33	100	80	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.27	100	75	100	0
Adverse events profile (Essential)	0.13	100	-100	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Influential)	0.27	80	60	100	0

Results of the decision conference:

- **Enhancement of the prototype model 1**
- Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2

Overview of the decision conference (March 31st)

- Brief presentation of the prototype model for the four clinical aspects.
- Development of a shared multicriteria model 1 based on group discussion of the prototype.
- Application of model 1 to calculate a clinical value score for each treatment.
- Development of a shared model 2 on non-clinical value aspects.
- Application of model 2 to calculate a non-clinical value score for each treatment.
- Discussion of the model outputs.

Participants

- INAMI participants:
 - Caroline Lebbe
 - Lisa Vervueren
 - Maëlle Anciaux
 - Marc Van De Castele
 - Piet Vancraeynest
 - Simon Roels
 - Anne Hendrickx
 - Filip Clinck

Clinical value aspects and respective descriptions and performance indicators that emerged from the decision conference

Clinical value aspects	Description and Performance indicators
Impact on mortality	Impact of the medicine on life expectancy. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Event-free survival, % of patients
Impact on morbidity	Impact of the medicine on symptoms and signs (non-fatal aspects related with the disease). <u>Indicators:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Proportion of infants sitting unassisted, assessed by Bayley Scales of Infant and Toddler Development (BSID), %
Tolerability to patients	The ability of the patient to tolerate the medicine as reflected by treatment discontinuation and treatment interruption or reduction. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • % of patients experiencing adverse events leading to discontinuation
Health related quality of life	Impact of the medicine on physical, emotional, mental and social wellbeing. <u>Indicator:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients able to feed orally and did not require nutritional support, %

- ‘Adverse events profile’ value aspect was eliminated since participants considered there was no difference in judgement between all three treatments and the comparator.
- A new value aspect was added: ‘Health related quality of life’
- During the decision conference, the indicator of the ‘Tolerability to patients’ value aspect was modified.

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on mortality'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 93% (STRIVE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +61%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 61% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +29%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 85% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 32% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference +53%

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on mortality'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on morbidity'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 37% (STR1VE US and EU maximum follow up 6 – 18 months) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +37%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza ~10% (clinical assumption) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +10%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 29% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC ~0% (clinical assumption) = difference ~ +29%

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on morbidity'

Clinical evidence on 'Tolerability to patients'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 9% (STR1VE US maximum follow up 18 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -30%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 16% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -23%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 0% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 39% (ENDEAR maximum follow up 13 months) = difference -39%

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Tolerability to patients'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

...between Zolgensma and Best Supportive Care

Zolgensma 75% (STR1VE US maximum follow up 18 months) vs BSC 0% (**clinical assumption**) = difference 75%

...between Spinraza and Best Supportive Care

Spinraza 25% (**clinical assumption**) vs BSC 0% (**clinical assumption**) = difference 25%

...between Evrysdi and Best Supportive Care

Evrysdi 74% (FIREFISH Part 2 maximum follow up 12 months) vs BSC 0% (**clinical assumption**) = difference 74%

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact on health related quality of life'

Relative weights for the clinical aspects derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments

Clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	Best Supportive Care
		#2	#3	#1	#4
CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		90	63.22	100	0
Health Related Quality of life (Essential)	0.25	100	42.86	100	0
Impact on mortality(Essential)	0.36	100	85	100	0
Impact on morbidity (Essential)	0.14	100	50	100	0
Tolerability to patients (Influential)	0.25	60	60	100	0

Clinical overall scores of each treatment

Treatments' profile

Results of the decision conference:

- Enhancement of the prototype model 1
- **Extending model building to include non-clinical value aspects - model 2**

Clinical evidence on 'Medicine's ease and convenience for patients'

Zolgensma

One-time IV infusion.

Spinraza

Administered orally once daily.

Evrysdi

Intrathecally; an induction period (4 loading doses) is followed by life-long repeated intrathecal administrations every 4 months.

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Medicine's ease and convenience for patients'

Clinical evidence on 'Mechanism of action'

Zolgensma

Recombinant AAV9-based gene therapy designed to deliver a copy of the gene encoding the human SMN protein.

Spinraza

Antisense oligonucleotide (ASO) designed to treat SMA caused by mutations in chromosome 5q that lead to SMN protein deficiency.

Evrysdi

Survival of motor neuron 2 (SMN2) splicing modifier designed to treat patients with SMA caused by mutations in chromosome 5q that lead to SMN protein deficiency.

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Mechanism of action'

Clinical evidence on 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Zolgensma

Provided at high specialist centres. Before administration of onasemnogene abeparvovec, baseline laboratory testing is required, including: AAV9 antibody testing using an appropriately validated assay, liver function: alanine aminotransferase (ALT), aspartate aminotransferase (AST), and total bilirubin, platelet count, and troponin-I.

Spinraza

Offered primarily at academic medical center. At baseline and prior to each dose, obtain a platelet count, coagulation laboratory testing, and quantitative spot urine protein testing.

Evrysdi

Administered at-home.

Values scores derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments on 'Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care'

Relative weights for the non-clinical value aspects derived from the decision conference group qualitative judgments

Non-clinical overall added-value of each treatment

		Zolgensma	Evrysdi	Spinraza
		#1	#2	#3
NON-CLINICAL VALUE ASPECTS		91.67	60	0
Ease and convenience for patients (Complementary)	0.70	100	50	0
Mechanism of action (Complementary)	0.25	100	0	0
Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care (Influential)	0.05	66.67	100	0

Non-clinical overall scores of each treatment

Appendix – Analyzing clinical and non-clinical treatments value

What-if analysis on clinical value aspects

Graph x-y

	Zolgensma	Spinraza	Evrysdi	BSC
Total cost of treatment with the drug (annual)	£ 1,795,000	£ 450 000,00	£ 100 288,80	£ 570,00